

GIFU UNIVERSITY

DOCTORAL DISSERTATION

Modelling and Simulation of Biosensors Driven by Myosin Motors

モーター蛋白質ミオシンによって駆動されるバイオセンサーのモデリングとシミュレーション

Author:

Samuel Macharia
Kang'iri

Supervisors:

Takahiro Nitta and
Minoru Sasaki

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Gifu University, Japan.

June 2, 2022

DECLARATION

I, Samuel Macharia Kang'iri (Sam Macharia), declare that this dissertation is original work and, to the best of my knowledge, has not been presented in any university or institution for a degree, or for consideration of any certification, and that external sources used here have been acknowledged in references.

Signature Date *3rd June, 2022*

Samuel Macharia Kang'iri
Reg. No. 11 8391 4101
Electronics and Information Systems Engineering Division,
Graduate School of Engineering,
Gifu University, Japan.

Approval

This dissertation has been submitted with my approval as the supervisor.

Signature Date

Prof. Takahiro Nitta (Ph.D.)
Department of Electrical, Electronic and Computer Engineering,
Applied Physics Course,
Gifu University, Japan.

This research was carried out in Prof. Takahiro Nitta Lab. [Applied Physics course, Electronics and Information Systems Engineering Division, Department of Electrical, Electronics, and Computer Engineering, Graduate School of Engineering, Gifu University, Gifu City, Japan.](#)

DEDICATION

To engineers who seek deeper insights

より深い洞察を求めるエンジニアへ

Kwa wahandisi wanaotafuta maarifa ya kina

Kũrĩ iijinia arĩa macaragia ũũgĩ mũrikĩru

 English

 Japanese

 Swahili

 Kikuyu

“In the fields of observation, chance
favours only the prepared mind.”

Lecture, University of Lille

LOUIS PASTEUR, DECEMBER 7, 1854

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An acknowledgement may be susceptible to *fundamental attribution error*.

ABSTRACT

Mechanical movement of animals is achieved by muscle contraction and relaxation. There are three types of muscles responsible for different movements in the body. First, skeletal muscles are attached to the bones and are responsible for body movements such as locomotion and pick-and-place tasks. Cardiac muscles are found in the heart and are essential for pumping blood throughout the body as needed. Smooth muscles are found in the trachea, intestinal wall, arteries, and veins and help move body fluids and materials. All of these muscles are driven by actin and myosin. Both skeletal and cardiac muscles are called striated muscles because they have a sarcomere, a repeated streak of actin and myosin. However, smooth muscles do not have the sarcomere and operate involuntarily. Underneath the smooth and striated muscle contraction and relaxation mechanism, the myosin biomolecular motors slide onto the actin filaments to allow the muscle mechanism to work. To elucidate the detailed working principle of these biomolecular motor systems, they can be extracted from muscle cells and used to perform *in vitro* motility assays. These motility assays are the basis for various micro-nano devices such as biosensors and biocomputers. Biomolecular motors are small in size, have high speed, low energy requirements, and high energy conversion efficiency. In the current state of engineering, it is still difficult to construct an artificial motor that can match the combined properties of these biomolecular motors. Understanding biomolecular motors is indispensable in physics and engineering. With this understanding, we can achieve biocompatible high-speed material transportation and control in micronanoscale engineering devices without constructing artificial nanoscale motors. Furthermore, it is easier to power devices based on biomolecular motors because only adenosine triphosphate (ATP) is required as a source of energy. ATP is ubiquitous and its chemical energy can be converted directly to mechanical energy (power stroke), and unlike conventional motors, heating is not involved. Myosin biomolecular motors and their associated actin filaments are the main focus of this study. Although myosin-driven devices generally have higher translation speeds, there are two main problems involved. First, when the *in vitro* motility assay is performed, some myosins become defective and need to be removed from the motility system because they introduce impedence. Second, actin filaments have high flexibility, which decreases the efficiency of cargo transport or drug delivery to the desired location due to their inherent intermittent wiggle. In the first problem, defective myosins bind to the actin filament and resist forward propulsion by staying stuck to the actin filament. It is difficult to quantitatively investigate the effects of these defective binding myosin in *in vitro* motility assay experiments. This difficulty arises from the inability to set the active ratio, the irreproducibility of an experiment with *in vitro* motility, and the spatiotemporal resolution. Instead, using computer simulation, we can set the active ratio and other parameters as needed. We can also simulate various motility assays with high reproducibility of the results. We can then iterate the simulation and analysis process to obtain testable results comparable to peer-reviewed experimental results. The simulation results are noteworthy because they can reveal a deeper understanding before the actual experiment is performed. These insights from the simulation results improve the

preparation of the experiments and build intuition of the experimental results. In this study, by developing a 3D Brownian dynamics simulation, we studied the effects of introducing these defective motors into an active actin-myosin system. We modelled the actin filament as a chain of rigid (inextensible) rods connected by beads. These rigid rods can bend around the beads. The assemblage of the rigid rods and beads makes a semi-flexible bead-rod polymer model equivalent to the mechanical properties of the actin filament. The myosin motors were modelled as linear springs with fixed spring constants equivalent to the experimental studies. To make the motility assay *in silico*, we generated these myosin motors randomly and distributed them uniformly on the surface of the substrate. Active and defective myosins were distinguished using different algorithm loops. Active myosin undergoes a nucleotide binding loop consisting of four main steps: binding to actin, performing a power stroke and propelling the actin filament, binding ATP and detaching from actin, and hydrolysing ATP to adenosine diphosphate and inorganic phosphate (ADP.Pi). Defective myosin undergoes one step: it binds to the actin filament, stays stuck, and detaches from the actin only if it experiences a force greater than the set detachment force. We adopted the threshold of the detachment force from the experiments, and in our simulation, a force beyond this threshold could cause either active or defective myosins to detach. To check the effect of defective myosin, we performed simulations with various active myosin ratios ranging from 10% to 100%. To validate the 3D simulation solution to the first problem, we developed a separate 1D mathematical model. In this mathematical model, we imitated the behaviour of defective motors by assuming that once bound to the actin filament, they stay bound and stretch along with the movement of the actin filament, and then snap off from the actin filament when the threshold of detachment force is exceeded. By analysing the results of the 3D simulation, we summarised the movement of the actin filament in the presence of defective myosin into three stages. When actin is stuck (active ratio < 90%), when actin wiggles with jerky movements (90% < active ratio < 92%), and when the actin filament is gliding continuously (active ratio \geq 94%). In this simulation, the continuous glide stage starts when defective myosins are reduced to approximately 10%. This continuous gliding stage is the one required for micro-nano device applications. In the first two stages, the motility assay may not be useful because the translation of the actin filaments is negligible. This implies that, in an actomyosin-based biosensor, a high active myosin binding ratio is required to initiate continuous translation. This finding was validated by the 1D mathematical model, which showed that actin filament movement began when defective myosins were reduced to around 20%. The discrepancy in the percentages of the continuous stage between the 3D simulation and the mathematical model may be attributed to the exclusion of thermal fluctuations and other factors in the 1D mathematical model. Both the 3D simulation and the 1D mathematical model showed a narrow range within which the actin filament can glide continuously over myosin motors. Consequently, an engineer should carefully choose the substrate used for the actomyosin-based application to favour the adherence and retention of the active myosin motors. In the second problem, to improve the efficiency of cargo/drug delivery by actin-based molecular shuttles, we sought to contain the high flexibility of the actin filaments by applying an external force field. Similar to the 3D simulation in the first problem, we adopted the same simulation to model the second problem by adding an external force field. When an external force field was applied to the actin filaments, the high flexibility of the actin filaments was restrained, consequently improving the efficiency of transport. The results of this study and the modelling and simulation techniques are useful in highly targeted drug delivery technologies.

Index Terms — *Biophysics, Biomechanics, Mathematical Modelling, Simulation, Biosensors, Biomedical Engineering.*

TABLE OF CONTENTS

DECLARATION	i
DEDICATION	ii
ACKNOWLEDGEMENT	iii
ABSTRACT	iv
TABLE OF CONTENTS	vi
LIST OF FIGURES	ix
LIST OF EQUATIONS	xii
LIST OF ALGORITHMS	xiii
ABBREVIATIONS	xiv
CHAPTER 1	
INTRODUCTION	1
1.1 Biomolecular Motors	2
1.1.1 The Muscle	2
1.1.2 <i>In Vitro</i> Motility Assay	4
1.1.3 Alternative Motors	5
1.2 Applications of Biomolecular Motors	7
1.2.1 Nanodevices Without Biomolecular Motors	7
1.2.2 Biomolecular Motor-based Nanodevices	9
1.3 Problem Statement	15
1.3.1 Molecular Shuttle Speed Limitation	15
1.3.2 High Flexibility of the Actin Filament	15
CHAPTER 2	
METHODOLOGY	17
2.1 Modelling and Simulation	18
2.1.1 Modelling	19
2.1.2 Simulation	19
2.1.3 Insights	20
2.2 Actin over Active and Defective Myosin: 3D Simulation	20
2.2.1 Unconstrained Actin Movement	23
2.2.2 Actin Bending Force Calculation	24
2.2.3 Actin and Myosin Contact	25
2.2.4 Forces Acting on Actomyosin	26
2.2.5 Myosin Detachment	27
2.2.6 Conversion of Myosin States	28

2.2.7	Myosin Placement	29
2.2.8	Simulation Validation	30
2.3	Actin Over Active and Defective Myosin: 1D Mathematical Model	32
2.4	Actin Under External Force: 2D Simulation	37
2.5	Path Persistence Length Calculation	37
CHAPTER 3		
RESULTS AND DISCUSSION		41
3.1	Actin over Active and Defective Myosin: 3D Simulation	42
3.1.1	Actin Conformation and Trajectory	42
3.1.2	Actin Filament Speed	46
3.1.3	Actin Filament Path Persistence Length	49
3.1.4	Myosin Binding to the Actin	52
3.1.5	Myosin Lifetime	61
3.2	Actin over Active and Defective Myosin: 1D Mathematical Model	64
3.2.1	Model Predictions	64
3.2.2	Model Applications	66
3.3	Actin under External Force: 2D Simulation	69
3.3.1	Effect on the Trajectories	69
3.3.2	Effect on Speed	71
3.3.3	Path Persistence Length	71
3.3.4	Biosensor Design Insight	76
3.4	Recommendations	77
CHAPTER 4		
CONCLUSION		79
4.1	Biosensor Design	79
4.2	Translation Mechanism	80
REFERENCES		82
APPENDIX		90
A	Simulation Program	91
A.1	Parameters Used	91
A.2	Main Program Implementation	92
A.3	Generate Normal Random Numbers	96
A.4	Bending Force Calculation	96
A.5	Initial Myosin Binding	96
A.6	Check Myosin-Actin Proximity	97
A.7	Binding Myosin	97
A.8	Myosin Step	98
A.9	Myosin Getting Stuck	98
A.10	Force Actin on Myosin	98
A.11	Forced Myosin Detachment	99
A.12	Force Acting on Actin Beads	100
A.13	Constraints	100
A.14	Renew the Myosin Population	101
A.15	Myosin State Conversion	103
B	Sample Analysis Programs	104
B.1	Path Persistence Length Calculation	104
B.2	Myosin Lifetime Calculation	107

C	Published Works	108
D	Recollections	109
INDEX		110

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LIST OF FIGURES

Figure 1.1: Muscle <i>in vivo</i> to <i>in vitro</i>	2
Figure 1.2: Actin-myosin structure	4
Figure 1.3: Hydrolysis cycle	4
Figure 1.4: <i>In vitro</i> motility assay	5
Figure 1.5: Alternative motors	6
Figure 1.6: Biosensor example	7
Figure 1.7: Lateral flow assay	8
Figure 1.8: Lab on a chip	8
Figure 1.9: Biosensor design sequence	9
Figure 1.10: Biosensor components	10
Figure 1.11: Fluorescence labeling	11
Figure 1.12: Biocomputation	12
Figure 1.13: Biosensor components	13
Figure 1.14: Surface imaging	14
Figure 1.15: Molecular shuttles with defective myosin	15
Figure 1.16: Actin flexibility	16
Figure 1.17: The problem statement	16
Figure 2.1: Simulation process	19
Figure 2.2: The simulation method	20
Figure 2.3: Unconstrained movement	23
Figure 2.4: Actin filament bending	24
Figure 2.5: Actin-myosin contact	25
Figure 2.6: Forces on beads	26
Figure 2.7: Myosin hydrolysis cycle	28
Figure 2.8: Myosin placement	29
Figure 2.9: Michaeli Menten's fitting	30
Figure 2.10: Speed and myosin density	31
Figure 2.11: Changing Δt	31
Figure 2.12: Active and defective myosin	32
Figure 2.13: Defective resistance F-V plot	33
Figure 2.14: Defective myosin dissociation cycle	34
Figure 2.15: Transition point	35
Figure 2.16: Continuous case	36
Figure 2.17: External force field	37
Figure 2.18: Actin persistence length	38
Figure 2.19: Persistence length example plot	39
Figure 3.1: Actin conformation changes	42

Figure 3.2: Actin filament trajectory	43
Figure 3.3: Actin spiral defects	44
Figure 3.4: Push-pull asymmetry	45
Figure 3.5: Actin Δt tip trajectories	46
Figure 3.6: Speed with various Δt	47
Figure 3.7: Actin filament speed	48
Figure 3.8: Effect on actin speed	48
Figure 3.9: Speed: various detachment forces	49
Figure 3.10: Trajectories: changing $r_{substrate}$	50
Figure 3.11: Path persistence at $r_{substrate} = 1.00$	50
Figure 3.12: Path persistence at $r_{substrate} = 0.98$	51
Figure 3.13: Path persistence at $r_{substrate} = 0.96$	51
Figure 3.14: Path persistence at $r_{substrate} = 0.94$	52
Figure 3.15: Path persistence: changing $r_{substrate}$	52
Figure 3.16: Instantaneous binding myosin	53
Figure 3.17: Mean binding myosin	54
Figure 3.18: Speed and binding relationship	55
Figure 3.19: Speed at MD2000	55
Figure 3.20: Speed at ATP500	56
Figure 3.21: Lifetime and binding ratio	56
Figure 3.22: Binding ratio: various detachment forces	57
Figure 3.23: Defective and active correlation	58
Figure 3.24: Speed and active correlation	58
Figure 3.25: Active fraction and speed correlation	59
Figure 3.26: Defective binding estimate	59
Figure 3.27: Binding time estimation	60
Figure 3.28: Defective binding prediction	61
Figure 3.29: Myosin lifetime comparison	62
Figure 3.30: Defective myosin lifetime	62
Figure 3.31: Myosin lifetime histogram	63
Figure 3.32: Load dependence comparison	63
Figure 3.33: Lifetime: various detachment forces	64
Figure 3.34: Myosin model solutions	64
Figure 3.35: Model prediction schematic	65
Figure 3.36: Solutions stability	66
Figure 3.37: Kinesin active ratios	67
Figure 3.38: Actin speed model prediction	68
Figure 3.39: Kinesin speed model	68
Figure 3.40: Mathematical gliding onset	69
Figure 3.41: Mathematical detachment forces	69
Figure 3.42: Negative force field trajectories	70
Figure 3.43: Positive force field trajectories	70
Figure 3.44: Force field effectiveness	70
Figure 3.45: Actin speed: simulation vs. experiment	71
Figure 3.46: Persistence changes with changing Δt	72
Figure 3.47: Sample trajectories $F=0$	72
Figure 3.48: Trajectories correlation plot $F=0$	73
Figure 3.49: Trajectories 10^{th} correlation plot $F=0$	74
Figure 3.50: Sample trajectories $F=+1$	74

Figure 3.51: Trajectories correlation plot $F=+1$	75
Figure 3.52: Sample trajectories $F=-1$	75
Figure 3.53: Trajectories correlation plot $F=-1$	76
Figure 3.54: Biomolecular rectifier	77
Figure 3.55: Channel trajectories comparison	78
Figure D.1: Supervisors and I	109
Figure D.2: Research work	109
Figure D.3: Defence	109

LIST OF EQUATIONS

Equation 1.1	Hydrolysis	5
Equation 2.1	Diffusion	23
Equation 2.2	Unconstrained movement	24
Equation 2.3	Actin bending force	25
Equation 2.4	Actin and myosin contact	25
Equation 2.6	Force actin on myosin	27
Equation 2.7	Random number generation	29
Equation 2.9	Michaeli Menten's fitting	30
Equation 2.10	$f - v$ relationship	33
Equation 2.11	Time averaged force	34
Equation 2.12	Impedance per active motor	34
Equation 2.13	Steady-state gliding speed	35
Equation 2.14	Critical velocity	35
Equation 2.15	Discontinuous transition	36
Equation 2.16	Continuous transition	37
Equation 2.17	Trajectory steps correlation calculation	38
Equation 2.18	Calculation of path persistence length	40
Equation 3.1	Binding motor estimation	59
Equation 3.3	Duty ratio estimation	60
Equation 3.4	Defective lifetime relation	61

LIST OF ALGORITHMS

Algorithm 1	The main program	22
Algorithm 2	Myosin binding proximity	26
Algorithm 3	Myosin forced detachment	28
Algorithm 4	Motor state conversion	29
Algorithm 5	Myosin placement	30
Algorithm 6	Trajectory average correlation	39

ABBREVIATIONS

AF	Actin filament
ATP	Adenosine triphosphate
ADP	Adenosine diphosphate
MD	Motor density
Bio-MEMS	Biomedical microelectromechanical systems
HMM	Heavy meromyosin
LMM	Light meromyosin
■	Indexed word
$r_{substrate}$	Substrate active motor ratio
R	Active motor ratio $r_{substrate}$
L_p	Path persistence length

INTRODUCTION

“Our main focus is a holistic understanding of the engineering principles applying to systems integrating molecular motors in general.”

Accounts of Chemical Research
HENRY HESS *et al.*, 2018

1.1	Biomolecular Motors	2
1.1.1	The Muscle	2
1.1.2	<i>In Vitro</i> Motility Assay	4
1.1.3	Alternative Motors	5
1.2	Applications of Biomolecular Motors	7
1.2.1	Nanodevices Without Biomolecular Motors	7
1.2.2	Biomolecular Motor-based Nanodevices	9
1.3	Problem Statement	15
1.3.1	Molecular Shuttle Speed Limitation	15
1.3.2	High Flexibility of the Actin Filament	15

This chapter introduces our study by providing important background information. Biomolecular motors are introduced and their engineering applications are discussed. Modelling and simulation are then introduced to outline their usefulness in research, particularly in this study. Finally, the problem statement is explained in detail.

1.1 Biomolecular Motors

Figure 1.1: From a skeletal muscle to actomyosin-based device. (a) Skeletal muscle, (b) Parts of a muscle, (c) Myofibril, (d) The sarcomere: actin and myosin *in vivo*, (e) Actin and myosin in *in vitro* motility assay

1.1.1 The Muscle

Various parts of a living animal generate movement. To survive, animals feed on plants or other animals and reproduce. For this reason, most animals move to find food and mates. Food digestion and reproduction processes also involve various movements. These movements are the result of muscle contraction and relaxation. There are three types of muscles found in animals: skeletal muscle, cardiac muscle, and smooth muscle [1]. As seen in Figure 1.1(a), the skeletal muscles are attached to the bones and are responsible for the locomotion between the bones. Cardiac muscles are found in the heart and are useful in pumping blood throughout the body. Skeletal and cardiac muscles are both termed striated muscles, as they consist of repeated parallel streak patterns called sarcomere (see Figure 1.1(d)). Smooth muscles are found in vessels, veins, and hollow organs and are responsible for the involuntary

movement of materials, through the contraction and relaxation of the actin and myosin filaments without sarcomere [1]. Despite the roles that muscle systems play in an animal, evolution has continued to favour various factors that promote muscle fitness, such as efficiency, speed, and low energy consumption [2].

Natural selection has optimised muscle construction according to animal requirements. A carnivorous animal, such as a cheetah, can run at a speed of around 104 km/h [3]. High speeds are required for predators and prey alike. However, this speed is occasional and is not necessary for herbivorous tortoises. Other animals, such as elephants, have optimised strength and ease of lifting. Today, the state of engineering motors has not yet matched the efficiency found in animal muscles. Understanding the natural solution to movement generation in animals may provide us with subtle solutions to achieving desired micro-scale movements.

Skeletal muscle consists of several fibres, which are essentially cylinder-shaped cells with a structure similar to that shown in Figure 1.1 (b). The myofibrils portrayed in Figure 1.1(c) are found in muscle cells and are approximately $1 \mu\text{m}$ in diameter, occupying more than 80% of muscle cells [4]. Around 2000 myofibrils are assembled to form a single muscle fibre [4], and additional assemblies make fascicles. The perimysium bundles up the fascicles, and the epimysium bundles up the perimysiums. Under microscopic observation, the myofibril shows distinct stripes called A and I bands, which are structures consisting of thick myosin filaments and thin actin filaments [5]. Figure 1.1 (d) shows the microscopic myofibril stripes that make up the sarcomere. The green stripes in Figure 1.1 (d) represent the myosin filaments, while the red stripes represent the Actin filaments. Figure 1.2 shows the same actin filament and myosin as in Figure 1.1 but in a little more detail. The thick myosin filaments are made up of myosin protein and are divided into two main parts: heavy meromyosin (HMM) and light meromyosin (LMM). HMM is divided into the binding part (S1), which is around $19 \mu\text{m}$, and the hinge part (S2). LMM is the part that adheres to the substrate. The actin-thin filament is made up of tropomyosin and troponin. Actin filaments are rope-like with a diameter around 7 nm . It is astounding that these cytoskeletal proteins have the potential to build cytoskeletal structures of dimensions of up to $1000 \mu\text{m}$.

Figure 1.2: The actomyosin. (a) The actin thin filament structure, and (b) The myosin thick filament structure

1.1.2 *In Vitro* Motility Assay

Figure 1.3: Myosin nucleotide binding. (a) *in vitro* motility assay, (b) myosin hydrolysis cycle

To understand the muscle mechanism or directly harness the functionality of biomolecular motors for artificial use, extraction from an animal muscle is performed. Figure 1.1 (e) presents an actomyosin motility assay *in vitro*. Since the first extraction of myosin on a glass surface *in vitro* motility assay by Kron *et al.* [6], various extraction protocols have been developed [7]. In general, actin and myosin are isolated from the muscle and then cleaned to minimise non-functional myosins. Various fluorescent techniques are used to help visualise actomyosin in action [8]. Figure 1.4 shows a *in vitro* motility assay in an experiment. An *in vitro* motility assay makes it easier to study various factors that affect or improve the actomyosin system. This kind of study is important to generate useful insights for *in vivo* and *in vitro*.

Figure 1.4: Actomyosin *in vitro* motility assay [9]. White lines are the actin filaments and the black background is the substrate.

For muscle contraction to occur *in vivo* and actin translation to occur *in vitro*, myosin undergoes four main processes. Figure 1.3 (b) shows the sliding contraction mechanism of the sarcomere, discovered by independent researchers [5]. In step (1), myosin hydrolyses ATP to ADP and inorganic phosphate, P_i (Equation (1.1)). This step is a recovery from the power stroke, and it allows myosin to relax, ready to bind to the actin filament. In step (2), myosin binds to the actin filament. In step (3), myosin contracts inward, which causes the actin filament to slide in. This step is called the power stroke, since the actin filament is propelled during this step. The chemical energy of ATP is converted directly to mechanical energy. In step (4), ATP binds to myosin, causing myosin to detach from the actin filament. Myosin can bind to the actin filament or ATP binds to myosin, but neither can happen at the same time. Sliding contraction occurs when steps (1) to (4) are repeated, not necessarily in that order.

1.1.3 Alternative Motors

The illustrations in Figure 1.1 focus on the basic parts that make up skeletal muscle and how actin and myosin can be extracted for applications *in vitro*. Although this figure may convey a systematic organisation and assembly of the muscle, the actual construction *in vivo* is rather complex [10]. In the cytoplasm of a cell, there exists a sophisticated network of interlinking proteins. This network is called the cytoskeleton. The cytoskeleton consists of protein filaments such as actin and the microtubule. The microtubules are tube-shaped with an outer diameter of approximately 25 nm and an inner diameter of approximately 18 nm [11]. Both microtubule and actin filaments grow out / polymerise from one end, called the plus-end. Cytoskeletal filaments combine to form large complex protein structures. For each filament, there is a corresponding motor protein that can bind to it. Motor proteins such as kinesin and myosin execute intracellular movements by progressively binding and detaching to microtubules or actin filaments, respectively. These movements play a key role in the organisation and shaping of cells. However, there are few microtubules in skeletal muscle [12], and actin and myosin have been

shown to be the basic building blocks of muscle.

Biomolecular motors are molecular nanomachines that can achieve cold conversion of chemical energy into mechanical work. In an *in vitro* motility assay, they have several engineering applications. In contrast to purely artificial motors, biomolecular motors are thermodynamically stable. Furthermore, the efficiency of biomolecular motors and their low energy requirements make them suitable candidates for the production of low-energy synthetic micro- to nanoscale devices [13][14][15][16][17][18][19]. Using advanced manufacturing techniques such as microfabrication, biomedical microelectromechanical systems (Bio-MEMS) such as biosensors [20][21][22][23][24], biocomputers [25], molecular communication devices [26][27], self-assembling circuits [28] and artificial muscles for soft robotics [29].

Figure 1.5 shows various nanoscale motors that could be used as an alternative to make nanodevices instead of actomyosin. While kinesin transports material by walking towards the plus-end of the microtubule filament, dynein motors transport material by walking towards the opposite side, as shown by the black arrows in Figure 1.5 (a). Microtubule filaments can achieve speeds ranging from $0.2 - 0.4 \mu\text{m/s}$. F1-ATPase performs a rotary motion as shown by the arrow in Figure 1.5 (b) and is useful in metabolism. Figure 1.5 (c) shows one of the smallest man-made nanoscale motors that can act as an alternative to nanoscale actuation. Among these alternatives, biomolecular motors have a promising efficiency greater than $> 50\%$. Actin filaments can reach speeds that are ten times higher than those of microtubules.

Figure 1.5: Alternative motors. (a) Kinesin and dynein biomolecular motor, (b) F1-ATPase rotational biomolecular motor [30], (c) Artificial nanoscale motor [31], [32]

1.2 Applications of Biomolecular Motors

1.2.1 Nanodevices Without Biomolecular Motors

Figure 1.6: Biosensor application example. Pancreatic cancer management [33]

The ability to detect and comprehend subtle changes in our surroundings has the potential to significantly enhance our quality of life. With our health intricately linked to the food we consume, the capability to identify anomalies in our diet holds paramount importance. A prime example is the detection of milk allergens, pivotal in mitigating complications stemming from milk consumption [34]. Similarly, in the realm of medicine, rapid and facile disease detection possesses life-saving implications. For instance, an affordable biosensor designed for early home detection of HIV/AIDS has revolutionized disease management [35]. Figure 1.7 depicts a paper-based lateral flow device, akin to those employed in the early detection of HIV/AIDS. Upon deposition of the analyte sample, capillary flow propels it along the device, facilitating the pickup and transportation of target molecules. If the sample contains suspected biomarkers, a specific coloration appears on the test line, indicating a positive result. Furthermore, biosensors play a crucial role in cancer management, particularly in biopsy procedures as illustrated in Figure 1.6. Moreover, precise drug delivery to targeted sites within the body holds immense potential for reducing adverse effects, particularly in cancer treatment [36], [37]. In forensic and road safety applications, biosensors, such as alcohol biosensors, aid in suspect identification, facilitating law enforcement efforts to restore order. Given their low-energy nature, biosensors hold promise for addressing a myriad of nanoscale challenges.

In essence, a biosensor serves as a device capable of recognizing specific biological or biochemical entities and converting them into a detectable and analyzable form. Typically, biosensors output electrical signals for convenient analysis and storage. Operating at nanoscale resolutions, biosensors are designed within the micro to

nanoscale range to accurately measure minute quantities. It's imperative that biosensors interact with biological systems without causing disruption or signal compromise. Additionally, ensuring the reproducibility of measured signals is crucial for analysis and verification purposes. As such, the development of robust and reliable biosensors is essential for advancing various fields in healthcare.

Figure 1.7: Biosensor application example. Early detection of HIV using lateral flow assay [38]

Electrochemical Biosensors

Figure 1.8: Lab on a chip [39]

Electrochemical biosensors offer a direct and efficient means of obtaining analytical results through interaction with biological entities. One exemplary application is the lab-on-a-chip (LOC) technology [40]. By analyzing electrochemical potentials, these biosensors can effectively identify and analyze interacting analytes. This analysis is typically based on changes in current, voltage, resistance, or other

electrical parameters occurring during the interaction. The direct nature of electrochemical analysis allows for rapid provision of analytical information.

In a LOC device, various fluid tests can be conducted within a confined area of just a few square millimeters, akin to performing experiments in a traditional laboratory setting. This compact format enables swift and efficient analysis, making it ideal for point-of-care diagnostics and field applications. By precisely programming the flow of fluids within the device, fast and accurate control can be achieved, leading to reproducible results [39].

The versatility of electrochemical biosensors, their capability to interface with biological systems offers immense potential across diverse applications. From medical diagnostics to environmental monitoring, electrochemical biosensors play a pivotal role in detecting and quantifying target analytes with high sensitivity and specificity. Furthermore, advancements in microfluidics and nanotechnology have facilitated the integration of electrochemical biosensors into miniaturized and portable devices, enabling rapid and on-site analysis. Additionally, ongoing research focuses on enhancing the selectivity and stability of electrochemical biosensors to broaden their applicability in various fields. Overall, electrochemical biosensors represent a powerful analytical toolset, poised to revolutionize the way we detect and monitor biological processes.

1.2.2 Biomolecular Motor-based Nanodevices

Biosensors

Figure 1.9: A design sequence of a biosensor driven by biomolecular motors [22]

Figure 1.10: Biosensor components

Figure 1.9 illustrates the three main stages that a biosensor driven by biomolecular motors can undergo. In the first step, the cargo or analyte is loaded to the filament. In the second step, a fluorescent tag is placed on the cargo to aid in its detection. This setup is also known as the molecular shuttle. In the last step, when the molecular shuttle delivers the analyte or cargo to the desired location, light is shown to the delivery location. By comparing the wavelength of the emitted light and that of the initial source, cargo delivery can be detected.

Figure 1.10 illustrates the four main components that make up a functional biosensor. The first component is the analyte, which is the entity to be detected and initiates the biosensor detection process. The detection or sensory component, also known as the bioreceptor, interacts with the analyte. Depending on the analyte in question, the result is unique. The signal transduction component converts the results from the sensory part to an electrical or optical signal. The signal processing component filters out any noise and amplifies the desired signal. The final part of the biosensor is the display or storage of the data obtained, depending on the intended application.

The basic working principle of a biosensor is the conversion of a biological entity to an electrical signal. For a biosensor to work, it needs to interact with the biological quantity being measured and provide the signal output of interest. There are various ways in which a biosensor can be made to detect an analyte. One way is by binding to the analyte, known as an affinity biosensor [41]. Another way is to react with the analyte, a method used by metabolic biosensors such as the flux sensor discussed by *Kochanowski et al.* [42]. Some biosensors combine with the analyte without a chemical reaction or active binding of the analyte. They are commonly known as catalytic biosensors. An example of a catalytic sensor is the catalytic hydrogen sensor [43]. The signal obtained from these kinds of detection is usually low and noisy and may need to be cleaned and amplified by microelectronics circuitry. Once the signal has been conditioned, it can be displayed or stored.

Molecular Recognition

Molecular recognition involves the formation of specific molecular bonds with target molecules, facilitating various biological processes. This recognition can occur through static or dynamic methods. In static interactions, two molecules combine to form a new compound, while dynamic interactions involve altering the association constants between interacting molecules [44]. Within biological systems, molecular binding plays a pivotal role in functions such as enzyme-substrate interactions, signal transduction, and cell-cell communication. These bonds encompass various types,

including electrostatic, hydrophobic, hydrogen, and inter-abundance bonding. Additionally, molecular recognition can be achieved through specific geometric binding via a process known as geometric imprinting, providing a tailored approach for selective molecular interactions.

It's imperative to explore its applications in various fields, including drug discovery, biomaterials engineering, and diagnostics. Leveraging the specificity of molecular interactions enables the design of biosensors capable of detecting target molecules with high sensitivity and selectivity. Furthermore, understanding the underlying principles of molecular recognition facilitates the development of novel therapeutic strategies, such as targeted drug delivery systems and molecular imaging techniques. Additionally, advancements in nanotechnology have led to the emergence of molecularly imprinted polymers, offering a versatile platform for molecular recognition in diverse applications, ranging from environmental monitoring to biomedical diagnostics.

Optical Detection Methods

Figure 1.11: Actin fluorescence check [45]

Optical detection methods offer versatile tools for molecular detection and analysis, harnessing the properties of light to probe molecular interactions. One such method, illustrated in Figure 1.11, utilizes fluorescence interference to track actin filaments [45]. In optical detection, target molecules can be identified either in their natural form or by employing fluorescent tags, enabling precise single-molecule detection and multiparametric analysis. Surface plasmon resonance, for instance, eliminates the need for fluorescence labeling by detecting changes in mass upon analyte binding, offering high sensitivity and interference-free detection. Conversely, fluorescence tagging methods involve coupling the analyte to a reagent responsive to light intensity, enabling the detection of analytes based on changes in reflected light intensity. Additionally, fluorescence protein-based methods present versatile tools for molecular detection and imaging, further expanding the scope of optical detection techniques [44].

Noninvasive Biosensors

Noninvasive biosensors encompass methods that enable analysis without the need for invasive procedures that penetrate the body to obtain samples. One exemplary approach is the saliva biosensor [46]. Saliva, derived from blood, carries

valuable metabolic information reflective of the body's physiological state. By analyzing biomarkers present in saliva, valuable insights into existing health conditions can be gleaned. Similarly, metabolic by-products such as sweat, breath, and tears offer potential sources of biomarkers indicative of various physiological states. These constituents can vary depending on the body's current condition, providing valuable diagnostic clues.

It's crucial to acknowledge the challenges associated with ensuring accuracy and reproducibility in testing conditions. Variations in sample composition, environmental factors, and individual differences can introduce complexities that may impact the reliability of results. Moreover, standardization of noninvasive sampling techniques and data interpretation methods remains a critical consideration to enhance the clinical utility of noninvasive biosensors. Despite these challenges, the noninvasive approach holds immense promise in revolutionizing diagnostic practices, offering a convenient and accessible means of monitoring health parameters without the need for invasive procedures.

Biocomputers

Figure 1.12: Biocomputation [25]

Biomolecular motors possess the potential to realize low-energy molecular microcomputers capable of solving combinatorial problems. Figure 1.12 illustrates the pursuit of a complete NP solution using guided microtubule channels as demonstrated by *Dan et al.* [25]. While silicon-based computers excel at sequential task execution, they face challenges in parallel processing. In contrast, microcomputers constructed from biomolecular motors offer a promising solution to this limitation.

Biomolecular motors exhibit inherent parallelism in their operation, allowing for the simultaneous execution of multiple tasks. This parallel processing capability can significantly enhance computational efficiency and enable the resolution of complex problems that would be impractical for traditional sequential computing

architectures. Furthermore, the use of biomolecular motors offers the potential for energy-efficient computing, leveraging biological systems' ability to perform complex tasks with minimal energy consumption. By harnessing the unique properties of biomolecular motors, researchers can pave the way for the development of novel computing paradigms capable of tackling a wide range of computational challenges with unprecedented efficiency and scalability.

Actomyosin-based Biosensors

Figure 1.13: Components of biomolecular-based biosensors. (a) Molecular shuttle, (b) *In vitro* motility assay, (c) Guiding track used to concentrate (y^+) or disperse (y^-) load, (c) Guiding track used to divide (y^-) or mix (y^+) load, (e) Concentrator device [23]

A typical biomolecular-based biosensor usually consists of a molecular shuttle, a guiding track, and a transducer. As shown in Figure 1.13, to make a molecular shuttle, linker proteins are attached to the actin filament and then the analyte or the cargo is attached to the linker. The cargo is then tagged with a fluorescent protein. This assemblage of tagged analyte linkers and the actin filament is driven by myosin motors adhered to the surface. Depending on the orientation of the adhered myosin, the actin filament and its cargo can move in a certain direction. A guiding track such as the one shown in Figure 1.13 (c) can be made to concentrate the cargo in a narrow channel or spread some cargo over a wide area. Figure 1.13 (d) shows another design of the guiding track that can divide the cargo into two channels or mix the cargo into

one channel. At the analyte detection point or the cargo delivery point, the fluorescence excitation light is shown (Figure 1.13 (e)). If the cargo has reached the detection point, their fluorescent tags will emit light in response to the excitation light. Excitation and emitted light are optically differentiated and transduced into an electrical signal. Figure 1.13 (f) [23] shows an application of actin and myosin as a fast concentrator device.

Surface Roughness Detection

Figure 1.14: Surface imaging [47]

Accurately measuring the roughness of nanoscale surfaces poses a significant challenge in various scientific and engineering fields. Traditional methods often struggle to provide precise measurements at such scales. However, emerging biomolecular implementations, utilizing components such as actin or microtubules, offer promising avenues for overcoming this challenge. Figure 1.14 showcases a tracking device utilizing microtubules, demonstrating its potential for nanoscale surface imaging [47]. By employing biomolecular motors, such as myosin, to traverse the surface, coupled with fluorescence imaging techniques, it becomes feasible to capture detailed information about surface roughness at the nanoscale level.

Biomolecular-based surface roughness detection systems present numerous advantages, including high sensitivity, scalability, and compatibility with nanoscale environments. Leveraging the inherent properties of biomolecular motors allows for precise and efficient surface scanning, facilitating advancements in fields such as nanotechnology, materials science, and biophysics. Furthermore, the integration of biomolecular components into surface imaging devices opens up new possibilities for characterizing complex surfaces with unprecedented accuracy and resolution.

Concentrator Devices

Molecular concentrator devices represent a crucial component in various analytical and diagnostic applications, offering the capability to converge or diverge analytes for subsequent analysis. *Lard et al.* introduced a concentrator device composed of actin and myosin components, as depicted in Figure 1.10(f). This innovative biosensor not only showcases portability but also achieves remarkable operational speeds, owing to its integration with actin and myosin. The inherent self-driving nature of this device

enables low-energy operation, making it highly suitable for diverse tasks, including drug delivery applications.

The utilization of biomolecular-based concentrator devices presents unparalleled opportunities for enhancing analytical capabilities and advancing biomedical technologies. These devices offer precise control over analyte concentration and localization, enabling targeted delivery and manipulation of molecular species. Moreover, their compatibility with biological systems makes them well-suited for *in vivo* applications, opening up new frontiers in drug delivery, diagnostics, and personalized medicine. By harnessing the power of biomolecular motors, researchers can continue to innovate and develop sophisticated concentrator devices with transformative implications for various fields of science and medicine.

1.3 Problem Statement

1.3.1 Molecular Shuttle Speed Limitation

Figure 1.15: Molecular shuttles with defective myosins

A major problem in the implementation of molecular shuttles integrated with actin and myosin is the denaturation of myosin when it adheres to the surface of the substrate. Denatured myosin, hereafter referred to as defective myosin, prevents the transportation of molecular shuttle cargo and needs to be cleaned [48]. Figure 1.17 (a) shows a realistic actin and myosin motility assay. This motility assay consists of active (green) and defective (blue) myosins that interact with the actin filament (red). Figure 1.3 (a) shows an ideal assay condition consisting of only active myosin driving the molecular shuttle. Unfortunately, when the motility assay in an experiment, some myosins become defective when adhering to a surface as shown in Figure 1.17 (b). When the active motors complete the hydrolysis cycle, the defective motors get stuck on the actin filament. This means that both active and defective motors can bind to the actin filament but, unlike the active motors, defective motors do not hydrolyse ATP. They cling to the actin filament opposing the forward movement until a greater force dislodges them from the actin filament. Here, we seek to articulate how the presence of defective myosin in a motility assay affects the functionality of a biosensor integrated with actin and myosin motors.

1.3.2 High Flexibility of the Actin Filament

Although actin filaments have the advantage of attaining speeds higher than those of other filaments such as microtubules, their bottleneck has high flexibility

(Figure 1.16 and [49]), making them exceptionally wiggly. The random movement of their trajectories contributed by the wiggly movement of the actin filaments' leading tips makes it difficult to predict the path that the designed molecular shuttles may follow. To design predictable devices, we need to understand how to control the random trajectory movements of the actin filaments.

Figure 1.16: Actin filament high flexibility makes it to wiggle around uncontrollably.

The Problem Statement Summary

Figure 1.17: Problem statement summary: (a) Defective myosin gets stuck on the actin filament and resists the forward movement. (b) Actin filament high flexibility makes it to wiggle around uncontrollably.

METHODOLOGY

“A basic model has the advantage of a few experimentally accessible parameters that can directly be validated, and can focus on the design of interconnected structures.”

Lab on a Chip

TAKAHIRO NITTA *et al.*, 2006

2.1	Modelling and Simulation	18
2.1.1	Modelling	19
2.1.2	Simulation	19
2.1.3	Insights	20
2.2	Actin over Active and Defective Myosin: 3D Simulation	20
2.2.1	Unconstrained Actin Movement	23
2.2.2	Actin Bending Force Calculation	24
2.2.3	Actin and Myosin Contact	25
2.2.4	Forces Acting on Actomyosin	26
2.2.5	Myosin Detachment	27
2.2.6	Conversion of Myosin States	28
2.2.7	Myosin Placement	29
2.2.8	Simulation Validation	30
2.3	Actin Over Active and Defective Myosin: 1D Mathematical Model	32
2.4	Actin Under External Force: 2D Simulation	37
2.5	Path Persistence Length Calculation	37

In this chapter, the methods used in modelling and simulation are discussed. To begin with, the methods and steps that were followed during the development of the 3D simulation are discussed. The second section discusses the development of the 1D mathematical model and the last section explains how the external force simulation was developed.

2.1 Modelling and Simulation

Biomolecular motors offer immense potential in the creation of microtransporters, such as molecular shuttles, with actomyosin demonstrating remarkable efficacy, particularly in applications demanding high speed [1]. These biomolecular-based microtransporters hold significant promise in advancing biosensor technology. However, reliance solely on experiments can present formidable challenges in accelerating biosensor development. Computational modeling and simulation play a crucial role in expediting this process. In this study, our focus lies on microtransporters powered by actin and myosin. Through simulation, we aim to elucidate how the presence of defective myosin in a motility assay impacts the functionality of a biosensor integrated with actin and myosin motors. Additionally, we seek to mitigate the high flexibility of actin filaments to constrain unpredictable movements. In simulation, precise specification of the active and defective myosin ratio is achievable, along with the manipulation of various parameters, ensuring high repeatability and minimal margin of error. Replicating the effects of electric fields on actin filaments observed in experiments will aid in comprehending and exploring diverse design possibilities for actin-based biodevices. While direct visualization of filaments has advanced considerably [50], simulations offer the advantage of circumventing spatio-temporal resolution limitations inherent in experimental setups.

Figure 2.1 presents a summary of our simulation methodology. Most modeling and simulation techniques adopt a reductionist approach, wherein the entire system is constructed by comprehending and amalgamating knowledge from smaller subsystems. These subsystems are then translated into equivalent mathematical models, which, during simulation, are propelled through time *in silico*. However, certain systems, like nutrition, may not lend themselves well to the reductionist approach [51]. In such cases, simulating the entire system as a black box can still yield valuable insights. Modeling and simulation serve as tools that augment our cognitive abilities. They enable us to revisit historical phenomena, delve deeper into current phenomena using the latest information, or even venture into the future by making plausible predictions. Systems like BioMEMS, equipped with biomolecular motors, pose significant challenges when relying solely on experimental methods. Computer simulation proves invaluable in furthering scientific understanding.

Figure 2.1: Modelling and simulation process

2.1.1 Modelling

The initial step in modeling a biological system entails comprehending its underlying mechanisms and operational principles. Once the system under study is identified, its operational principles are deconstructed into modules or functions, each representing a specific process or aspect of the system. Information utilized primarily stems from real-life experiments and the amalgamation of mathematical and physical principles to create equivalent representations of the biological system. These representations can be analytically solved. This process, henceforth referred to as modeling, entails conceptual formulation and the creation of appropriate mathematical formulations that either represent or are analogous to the concept. A validation process is imperative to ascertain whether the constructed model accurately mirrors the real-world problem being addressed. These steps are iterated during model construction to ensure all pertinent facts are incorporated and adequately represented.

2.1.2 Simulation

In the simulation process (refer to Figure 2.1), the models are executed over time using computer programs. Mathematical model representations are translated into computer programs using a sequential scheme. When simulating subsystems performing specific functions, the computer program is developed in terms of modules specifying the algorithm the computer must follow. This process entails testing small portions of the developed program to verify that expected results align with the real-world problem. Depending on program complexity, adjustments can be made to optimize computer processing power and simulation duration. During program execution, inputting or outputting several files may be necessary, requiring efficient file management to ensure program efficiency. Program development, execution, and input-output management are iterated as necessary during the

simulation process.

2.1.3 Insights

Simulation results should provide evidence, suggestions, insights, or facilitate the formulation of pertinent questions about the primary problem at hand. Following completion of the simulation program, output data undergoes analysis. Analysis results are compared with expected outcomes from real-world experiments and anticipated analytical results from mathematical models. If these findings align, further analysis and simulation are pursued to deepen understanding of the system. In cases where simulation outcomes diverge from expected results, further modeling and simulation iterations are undertaken to rectify potential bugs. The iterative process of simulation, data analysis, and comparison with known system facts should lead to enhanced understanding, significant predictions, or the discovery of new system insights. It's crucial to validate every insight gained from simulation to mitigate the risk of errors or misinterpretations.

2.2 Actin over Active and Defective Myosin: 3D Simulation

Figure 2.2: The simulation method. (a) the in vitro motility assay, (b) conceptual model of the in vitro motility assay - the in silico motility assay.

This section explains the mathematical equations that were employed in making the simulation program of the actin filament and myosin in an in vitro motility assay. An explanation of how the mathematical models may be executed in a computer program is provided. A pseudo code is also provided to elucidate a general implementation free from a specific computer language. In sections where it is applicable, references to the FORTRAN code that was used in this simulation are

provided. The pseudo code in Algorithm 1 summarizes how various functions of the main code were implemented.

The simulation method used in this study is in part adapted and expounded from *Ishigure et al.* [52]. As illustrated in Figure 2.2, the actin filament is modelled as a set of rigid rods connected with beads. These rods can bend about the beads with a flexural rigidity, EI , set to $0.073 \text{ pN}\cdot\mu\text{m}^2$ [49]. Both active and defective myosin are modelled as linear springs with spring constant of $300 \text{ pN}/\mu\text{m}$ [53], and detach force of 9.2 pN [54]. The difference between active and defective myosin is that while active myosin binds to the actin filament through the ATP hydrolysis cycle, the defective ones bind to the actin filament and only detach if forced to dislodge by the detach force. This actin-myosin simulation is implemented in a Brownian dynamics environment. The

following are the key components that make up our simulation.

```

1 Declare variables and parameters; // line 1-36
2 Set initial conditions; // line 45-57
3 Prepare output files; // line 60-76
4 Set initial conformation of the actin filament; // line 77-86
5 Set initial location and states of myosin tails; // line 87-91
6 function CALL CheckMotorFilamentProximity is // line 95-96
7 | Checking the proximity between the actin and myosin ;
8 function CALL InitialMotorBinding is // line 98-99
9 | Checking binding of motor at the initial time step;
10 function CALL CalculateForceMotor is
11 | Calculating the force acting on the motor; // line 101-103
12 | Calculating the force acting on the bead by motors;
13 | Calculating the total force acting on the bead; // line 104-110
14 Outputs; // line 112-128
15 repeat // line 130
16 | case Update motor states do
17 | | function CALL MotorForcedDetachment is // line 135-139
18 | | | Forcing detachment of motors;
19 | | function CALL MotorStateConv is // line 153-160
20 | | | Converting myosin states ;
21 | | if Myosin binds to the actin then // line 140-152
22 | | | Check proximity between filament and motor; // line 142
23 | | | Check if motors bind to the filament with binding rate  $k_a$  ;
24 | | | Check myosin state conversion upon binding; // line 153-160
25 | | function CALL RenewMotorPopulation is // line 161-167
26 | | | Renewing Motor Population;
27 | case Update bead positions do
28 | | Generate random number matrices; // line 169-215
29 | | Prepare vector representation for position, force, and random numbers ;
30 | | repeat // line 216-240
31 | | | Perform unconstrained movements of beads
32 | | | until Constraint and confinement are Satisfied;
33 | | | Update position variables of beads; // line 249-259
34 | case Prepare force variables do
35 | | function CALL CalculateForceMotor is // line 260-263
36 | | | Calculating the force acting on the motor; // line 261-263
37 | | function CALL CalculateForceBead is
38 | | | Calculating the force acting on the bead by motors; // line 264
39 | | | Calculating the total force acting on bead; // line 267-270
40 | Outputs; // line 271-291
41 until Set time elapses;

```

Algorithm 1: Actin-myosin motility assay main program. The line numbers referenced within the comments ‘//’, refers to the main program in Appendix A.2

2.2.1 Unconstrained Actin Movement

To model the movement of the actin filament from one point to the next, we take into consideration the fluid drag, myosin tension, and thermal effects. In our simulation, the actin filament is made up of an assemblage of rigid rods joined together by bead points as illustrated by Figure 2.2. The movement of these bead points in this Brownian environment is unconstrained, and the global protein motion is assumed to be overdamped. The inertial forces are neglected since the viscous forces are much greater [11]. We used the explicit method by computing the later state of our system $X_i(t + \Delta t)$ using the current state $X_i(t)$ [55].

Figure 2.3 illustrates the derivation in Equations (2.2). In the following equations, let γ be the drag coefficient, BL be the actin filament bond length, $\vec{F}_{m,i}$ be the myosin tension force, $\vec{F}_{a,i}$ to be the actin filament bending, and \vec{R}_i to represent the thermal fluctuations. The value 0.001 is the viscosity, η , of the surrounding fluid (water) and 0.006 is the actin filament diameter in μm [11], [56]. The variable $\sqrt{2D\Delta t}\vec{N}(0, 1)$ is the diffusion coefficient contributed by thermal fluctuations and Brownian movement. The change in time, Δt , must be optimum in such a way that it is sufficiently small for better accuracy and not too small to make the computer computation time unnecessarily long.

Figure 2.3: Unconstrained actin-myosin interaction. $F_{m,i}$ represent the force acting on myosin and $F_{a,i}$ represent the bending of the actin filament

$$\gamma = \frac{3\pi \times 0.001 \times BL}{\log\left\{\frac{BL}{0.006}\right\}} \quad (2.1a)$$

$$D = \frac{k_B T}{\gamma} \quad (2.1b)$$

$$\gamma \frac{d\vec{X}_i}{dt} = \vec{F}_{m,i} + \vec{F}_{a,i} + \vec{R}_i \quad (2.2a)$$

$$\gamma \int_t^{t+\Delta t} \frac{d\vec{X}_i}{dt} dt = \int_t^{t+\Delta t} \vec{F}_{m,i} dt + \int_t^{t+\Delta t} \vec{F}_{a,i} dt + \int_t^{t+\Delta t} \vec{R}_i dt \quad (2.2b)$$

$$\int_t^{t+\Delta t} d\vec{X}_i = \frac{\Delta t}{\gamma} \vec{F}_{m,i} + \frac{\Delta t}{\gamma} \vec{F}_{a,i} + \frac{1}{\gamma} \int_t^{t+\Delta t} \vec{R}_i dt \quad (2.2c)$$

$$\vec{X}_i(t + \Delta t) - \vec{X}_i(t) = \frac{\Delta t}{\gamma} \vec{F}_{m,i} + \frac{\Delta t}{\gamma} \vec{F}_{a,i} + \sqrt{2D\Delta t} \vec{N}(0,1) \quad (2.2d)$$

$$\boxed{\vec{X}_i(t + \Delta t) = \vec{X}_i(t) + \frac{\Delta t}{\gamma} \vec{F}_{m,i} + \frac{\Delta t}{\gamma} \vec{F}_{a,i} + \sqrt{2D\Delta t} \vec{N}(0,1)} \quad (2.2e)$$

2.2.2 Actin Bending Force Calculation

The actin filament rigid rods are modelled in such a way that they can bend about beads. The amount of bending depends on the set flexural rigidity, EI , and the bond length of the rods that make up the actin filament. To elucidate the actin filament bending force, $\vec{F}_{a,i}$, the actin filament in Figure 2.4 is depicted as 3 beads (\vec{R}_1 , \vec{R}_2 , and \vec{R}_3) connected with 2 rigid rods. Here, \vec{U}_{12} and \vec{U}_{23} are unit vectors of $\vec{R}_1-\vec{R}_2$ and $\vec{R}_2-\vec{R}_3$, respectively. The bending force can be expressed as follows.

Figure 2.4: Actin filament bending

Assuming the number of beads = 3,

$$\text{let } U = \frac{1}{2} \frac{EI}{d^3} \sum_{i=2}^{n-1} (\vec{R}_{i+1} - 2\vec{R}_i + \vec{R}_{i-1})^2 \quad [57](Eq.5) \quad (2.3a)$$

$$\text{let } F_i = \frac{1}{2} \frac{EI}{d^3} (\vec{R}_3 - 2\vec{R}_2 + \vec{R}_1)^2 \quad (2.3b)$$

$$= \frac{1}{2} \frac{EI}{d} (\vec{U}_{23} - \vec{U}_{12})^2 \quad (2.3c)$$

$$= \frac{1}{2} \frac{EI}{d} \left(\frac{\vec{R}_3 - \vec{R}_2}{d} - \frac{\vec{R}_2 - \vec{R}_1}{d} \right)^2 \quad (2.3d)$$

To calculate force from the potential energy, the acting bending force,

$$F_{a,i} = \frac{1}{2} \frac{EI}{d^3} \sum_{j=2}^{n-1} (\vec{R}_{j+1} - 2\vec{R}_j + \vec{R}_{j-1})^2 \quad (2.3e)$$

This can be implemented as shown in Appendix A.4

2.2.3 Actin and Myosin Contact

Figure 2.5 shows a segment of an actin filament (red line) and myosin (green spring) binding to it. This system is in a 3D space. Bead 1 represents a point on the actin filament segment located at a point $(X_{i,j}, Y_{i,j}, Z_{i,j})$ and bead 2 a point located at $(X_{i,j+1}, Y_{i,j+1}, Z_{i,j+1})$ towards the plus-end. The distance between bead 1 and the point of contact, c , is the intercept, e .

Figure 2.5: Actin and myosin contact

If the actin filament is within the radius, r , from myosin tail, m , the myosin can bind to it. This radius is hereafter referred to as the *capture radius* and it is taken to be 20 nm [58], [59], unless otherwise stated. The intercept e is given by the dot product of vector, \vec{B} , and vector, \vec{A} , divided by the actin bond length, B_L .

$$e = \frac{\vec{B} \cdot \vec{A}}{B_L} \quad (2.4a)$$

$$\vec{B} = \begin{bmatrix} Xm - X_{i,j} \\ Ym - Y_{i,j} \\ Zm - Z_{i,j} \end{bmatrix}; \vec{A} = \begin{bmatrix} X_{i,j+1} - X_{i,j} \\ Y_{i,j+1} - Y_{i,j} \\ Z_{i,j+1} - Z_{i,j} \end{bmatrix} \quad (2.4b)$$

$$S^2 = |B|^2 + e^2 \quad (2.4c)$$

$$|B|^2 = \Delta x^2 + \Delta y^2 + \Delta z^2 \quad (2.4d)$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} Xc \\ Yc \\ Zc \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} X_1 \\ Y_1 \\ Z_1 \end{bmatrix} + e - c \begin{bmatrix} X_2 - X_1 \\ Y_2 - Y_1 \\ Z_2 - Z_1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (2.4e)$$

From here, the possible contact points, c_{temp} , between bonds and myosin are calculated, and the myosin motor makes a stride. Based on the probability, the decision is made on whether the binding actually occurs and the unwanted points of no contact are discarded. Myosin binds to the actin filament via the shortest point from its tail, m , to the actin point of contact, c . Myosin step is made by taking

$stepsize/bondlength$. The new myosin contact state is calculated as shown in Equation (2.5). A program to check for myosin-actin contact was implemented as shown in Algorithm 2.

$$ContactState = c_{temp} + \frac{Stepsize}{B_L} \quad (2.5)$$

```

1 SUBROUTINE CheckMotorFilamentProximity;           // Appendix A.6
2 SUBROUTINE MotorBinding;                         // Appendix A.7
3 SUBROUTINE MotorStep;                           // Appendix A.8
4 SUBROUTINE MotorStuck;                          // Appendix A.9
5 case SUBROUTINE CheckMotorFilamentProximity do
6   if Active/defective motor is unbound, ready-to-bind ( $M \cdot D \cdot P$  state), and within
   capture radius then
7     Set TempContact;
8     Leave ContactState the same;
9 case SUBROUTINE MotorBinding do
10  if Active/defective motor is unbound, ready-to-bind ( $M \cdot D \cdot P$  state), and within
   capture radius then
11    case Active motors (SUBROUTINE MotorStep) do
12      Make a step on actin filament;
13    case Defective motors (SUBROUTINE MotorStuck) do
14      Motor gets stuck on the filament;
15  else
16    Set TempContact = 0.0;

```

Algorithm 2: Filament proximity and myosin binding

2.2.4 Forces Acting on Actomyosin

In Figure 2.6, the green linear spring represents a myosin motor and the red rod represents the actin filament rigid rod. The actin filament has a unit length of 1 ($2 - 1 = 1$). Force F_1 acts on bead 1 while force F_2 acts on bead 2 of the actin filament. Force F_m acts on the myosin motor. The delta, Δ , in Figure 2.6 represents the perceived center of mass of mass.

Figure 2.6: Forces actin on beads

The distance from the center of mass to the point where myosin binds to the actin filament is denoted by x . The intercept, e , is the distance between the first bead and the

myosin binding contact on the actin filament. The myosin binding forces are derived in Equation (2.6). The sum of the counterclockwise moments, $\sum \curvearrowright mom$, is equal to the sum of clockwise moments, $\sum \curvearrowleft mom$.

$$\sum \curvearrowright mom = \sum \curvearrowleft mom \quad (2.6a)$$

$$\frac{1}{2} \times F_1 = (x \times F_m) + \left(\frac{1}{2} \times F_2\right) \quad (2.6b)$$

$$e = \frac{1}{2} + x; x = e - \frac{1}{2} \quad (2.6c)$$

$$\frac{1}{2} F_1 = \left(e - \frac{1}{2}\right) F_m + \frac{1}{2} F_2 \quad (2.6d)$$

$$\boxed{F_m = F_1 + F_2} \quad (2.6e)$$

$$F_1 = F_m - F_2; F_2 = F_m - F_1 \quad (2.6f)$$

Substituting Equation (2.6f) into Equation (2.6d):

$$\frac{1}{2} F_1 = \left(e - \frac{1}{2}\right) F_m + \frac{1}{2} (F_m - F_1) \quad (2.6g)$$

$$\boxed{F_1 = e \times F_m} \quad (2.6h)$$

$$\frac{1}{2} (F_m - F_2) = \left(e - \frac{1}{2}\right) F_m + \frac{1}{2} F_2 \quad (2.6i)$$

$$\boxed{F_2 = (1 - e) \times F_m} \quad (2.6j)$$

2.2.5 Myosin Detachment

When an active or defective myosin is attached to the actin filament, its detachment from the filament depends on the force acting on it. The contact state of a given myosin is after its detachment has been handled. As illustrated in Algorithm 3, when the set detach force exceeds the actual force on the myosin head, the myosin is forced to detach from the filament and the force acting on the myosin is reset to 0. For the case of active myosin, the contact state is updated to -1 and for the case of defective myosin,

the contact state is updated to 0.

```

1 CALL MotorForceDetachment; // Appendix A.11
  Input: F_Motor_X, F_Motor_Y, F_Motor_Z, Release_ADP, ContactState
2 case Active motors do
3   if force acting on motor heads > detachment force then
4     Set the force acting on the motor to be 0;
5     Set the ContactState to be  $-1.0(M \cdot ATPstate)$ ;
6     Set the ReleaseADP = 0;
7 case Defective motors do
8   if force acting on motor heads > detachment force then
9     Set the force acting on the motor to be 0;
10    Set the contact state to be 0.0 (unbound state);
  Output: F_Motor_X, F_Motor_Y, F_Motor_Z, Release_ADP, ContactState

```

Algorithm 3: Forced detachment of motors

2.2.6 Conversion of Myosin States

The myosin nucleotide binding used in our simulation followed the steps illustrated in Figure 2.7. An active myosin motor undergoes these four main steps in a hydrolysis cycle. Myosin step size was taken to be 10 nm [58].

Figure 2.7: Myosin hydrolysis cycle. (a) myosin nucleotide binding states, (b) simulated conversion of active myosin states, adapted from *Ishigure et al.* [52]. A: Actin filament, M: Myosin, T: ATP, D.P: ADP+Pi, D: ADP

```

1 CALL MotorStateConv; // Appendix A.15
2 Applies only to active motors;
3 case (1.) Myosin · ADP · Pi state (M.D.P: ContactState=0) do
4 | Convert to myosin · ATP state with the probability of  $k_{hm} * dt$ ;
5 case (2.) Actin · Myosin · ADP · Pi state (A.M.D: ContactState≥1; Release_ADP=0) do
6 | Calculate the tangential force;
7 | Calculate  $k_d$ ;
8 | Convert to Actin · Myosin state with the probability of  $k_d * dt$ ;
9 case (3.) Actin · Myosin · ATP state (A.M: ContactState≥1; Release_ADP=1) do
10 | Convert to Myosin · ADP · Pi state with the probability of  $k_{hp} * dt$ ;
11 case (4.) Myosin · ATP state (M.T: ContactState=-1) do
12 | Convert to Myosin · ADP · Pi state with the probability of  $k_{hp} * dt$ ;

```

Algorithm 4: Motor state conversion

2.2.7 Myosin Placement

To make motility assays, we place myosin randomly but in a way that is uniformly distributed across the surface. We provide two sources of uniformly distributed random numbers, U_1 and U_2 , of range $[0, 1]$, and then apply the Box-Muller transformation [60] to output independent random numbers with a standard normal distribution. The N value in Equation (2.7) is the output to be placed as myosin. This placement mimics the myosin motors on the surface of a glass plate in an in vitro motility assay.

$$N = \sqrt{-2\log U_1} \times \cos(2\pi U_2) \quad (2.7)$$

Figure 2.8 illustrated how myosin motors were erased (E) and added (A) as the actin filament progressed throughout the simulation.

Figure 2.8: Myosin placement as the actin filament moves from one point to another.

```

1 SUBROUTINE RenewMotorPopulation; // Appendix A.14
2 Erase old motor region;
3 Update EraseCounter and ActiveMotorIdxOffset;
4 if Any bead is near boundary then
5   Generate a new motor region;
6   Generate temporal x- and y-coordinates of motor tails;
7 if Temporal x- and y-coordinates are appropriate then
8   Update AddedMotorCounter;
9   Accept the temporal coordinates as new XM and YM;
10  Assign MotorType and ContactState;

```

Algorithm 5: Myosin placement

The Equation (2.8) was used in the simulation as the load dependence function.

$$k_d = k_d^0 \exp\left(-\frac{F \delta x}{k_B T}\right) \tag{2.8}$$

Table 1 shows a list of variables used during a typical simulation. Some of these values were changed accordingly as explained in the results and discussion section.

2.2.8 Simulation Validation

Figure 2.9: Michaeli Menten’s fitting

$$y = mx + c \tag{2.9a}$$

$$\frac{1}{v} = \frac{K_m}{V_{max}} \times \frac{1}{ATP} + \frac{1}{V_{max}} \tag{2.9b}$$

$$V_{max} = \frac{1}{intercept}, K_m = V_{max} \times slope \tag{2.9c}$$

To validate that our simulation correlates with the Michaeli Menten’s kinetics, we ran several simulations of varying ATP concentrations as shown in Figure 2.9.

Equation (2.9c) was used to calculate the maximum velocity and the K_m value.

Figure 2.10: Speed changes with changing myosin density.

The actin filament speed stability with changing myosin density was tested in a simulated motility assay of 100% active myosin ratio. As plotted in Figure 2.10, it was observed that running the simulation at a low motor density of, say, $500 \mu m^{-2}$, would yield highly fluctuating actin filament speeds characterized by detachment. For this reason, we ran all simulations at $3000 \mu m^{-2}$, unless otherwise stated. A myosin density of $3000 \mu m^{-2}$ and above provides a relatively stable actin filament speed. However, a motility assay of around $4000 \mu m^{-2}$ would be unrealistic since it would be too cluttered with myosin.

Figure 2.11: Variations caused by a change in Δt in simulation computations.

Before moving on to the simulation program, it is important to check if the preliminary results are stable and reliable. To carry out this test in our simulation, we ran several simulations of changing active ratios while changing the simulation Δt as

shown in Figure 2.11. The smaller the precision of Δt , the more accurate our simulation computation is likely to be. However, if Δt is allowed to be too small, the computation time becomes unnecessarily long. In this simulation, we used $\Delta t = 1 \times 10^{-7}$ since at this point, the computations had already stabilized.

2.3 Actin Over Active and Defective Myosin: 1D Mathematical Model

This section explains the method used to develop a separate 1D mathematical model to validate the results of the 3D simulation. In this model, defective motors are represented in blue and are modelled to stay stuck to the actin filament once bound. As the actin filament is propelled by other motors, the bound defective motor is stretched to the point where it is forced to detach.

Figure 2.12: Active and defective myosin

The gliding speed, V , of the actin filament, AF, shown in Figure 2.12 is affected by a resisting force, f , caused by the defective motor. When f is zero, the actin filament will move at a maximum speed, V_{max} . However, as f increases, the actin filament slows down. As shown in Figure 2.13, if f is large enough ($= f_{stall}$), the actin filament will stop moving. Beyond f_{stall} , the actin filament may detach.

Figure 2.13: Active-defective force-velocity relationship: V_{max} vs. f_{stall}

The force-velocity relationship is expressed as in Equation (2.10), where V_{max} is the maximum gliding speed, f_{stall} is the stall force of a myosin, and f is the external force per active myosin. Note that $f, f_{stall} < 0$ because they are opposing the translation of the actin filament.

$$v(f) = \begin{cases} v_{max}(1 - \frac{f}{f_{stall}}), & \text{for } f_{stall} < f < 0 \\ 0, & \text{for } f < f_{stall} \end{cases} \quad (2.10)$$

Defective myosins effectively work as friction by impeding actin filament translation through repeated binding and dissociation. As illustrated in Figure 2.14, the defective myosin binds to the actin filament at a binding rate of $1/\tau_1$ and it stays stuck. As the actin filament continues to move, the defective myosin is made to elongate and eventually at a rupture force, f_{rupt} , after a time, τ_2 , it is forced to detach from the filament. The time τ_2 depends on the actin filament speed and the rupture force of the defective myosin. Time T is the total time for the whole period from bind to detach. The time-averaged force generated by a defective motor, $\overline{f_{def}}$, as illustrated in Figure 2.14 and is derived as shown in Equation (2.11).

Figure 2.14: Binding and dissociation cycle of a defective myosin

$$\overline{f_{def}} = \lim_{\tau \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{T} \int_0^T f_{def}(t) dt \quad (2.11a)$$

$$= \frac{1}{\tau_1 + \tau_2} \int_0^{\tau_1 + \tau_2} f_{def}(t) dt \quad (2.11b)$$

$$= \frac{1}{\tau_1 + \tau_2} \times \frac{1}{2} f_{rupt} \tau_2 \quad (2.11c)$$

$$= \frac{f_{rupt}}{2(1 + \frac{\tau_1}{\tau_2})} \quad (2.11d)$$

$$\boxed{= \frac{f_{rupt}}{2(1 - \frac{kV\tau_1}{f_{rupt}})}} \quad \because \tau_2 = -\frac{f_{rupt}}{kv}, \text{ Hooke's law } f = ke \quad (2.11e)$$

Calculating the impedance per active motor, f_{imp} :

$$f_{imp} = \frac{\rho_d L}{\rho_a L} \times \overline{f_{def}} \quad (2.12a)$$

$$\boxed{= \frac{\rho_d}{\rho_a} \times \frac{f_{rupt}}{2(1 - \frac{kV\tau_1}{f_{rupt}})}} \quad (2.12b)$$

Steady state gliding speed:

Substituting Equation (2.12b) into Equation (2.10):

$$v = v_{max} \left(1 - \frac{\rho_d}{\rho_a} \times \frac{1}{2(1 - \frac{kv\tau_1}{f_{rupt}})} \times \frac{f_{rupt}}{f_{stall}} \right) \quad (2.13a)$$

$$\left(1 - \frac{kv\tau_1}{f_{rupt}} \right) v = v_{max} \left(\left(1 - \frac{kv\tau_1}{f_{rupt}} \right) - \frac{f_{rupt}}{2f_{stall}} \times \frac{\rho_d}{\rho_a} \right) \quad (2.13b)$$

$$v - \frac{k\tau_1}{f_{rupt}} v^2 = v_{max} - \frac{kv_{max}\tau_1}{f_{rupt}} v - \frac{v_{max}f_{rupt}}{2f_{stall}} \times \frac{\rho_d}{\rho_a} \quad (2.13c)$$

$$\frac{k\tau_1}{f_{rupt}} v^2 - \left(1 + \frac{kv_{max}\tau_1}{f_{rupt}} \right) v + v_{max} \left(1 - \frac{f_{rupt}}{2f_{stall}} \times \frac{\rho_d}{\rho_a} \right) = 0 \quad (2.13d)$$

$$v = \frac{f_{rupt}}{2k\tau_1} \left(1 + \frac{kv_{max}\tau_1}{f_{rupt}} \pm \sqrt{\left(1 + \frac{kv_{max}\tau_1}{f_{rupt}} \right)^2 + \frac{4kv_{max}\tau_1}{f_{rupt}} \left(1 - \frac{f_{rupt}}{2f_{stall}} \times \frac{\rho_d}{\rho_a} \right)} \right) \quad (2.13e)$$

At the transition:

Figure 2.15: Transition point

$$v_c = \frac{f_{rupt}}{2k\tau_1} \left(1 + \frac{kv_{max}\tau_1}{f_{rupt}} \right) \quad (2.14a)$$

$$= \frac{v_{max}}{2} + \frac{f_{rupt}}{2k\tau_1} \quad (2.14b)$$

The transition is continuous if $v_c \leq 0$ and discontinuous if $v_c > 0$. The critical active motor ratio, R_c , for the discontinuous transition is derived as in Equation (2.15).

$$\left(1 + \frac{kv_{max}\tau_1}{f_{rupt}}\right)^2 - \frac{4kv_{max}\tau_1}{f_{rupt}} \left(1 - \frac{f_{rupt}}{2f_{stall}} \times \left(\frac{\rho_d}{\rho_a}\right)_c\right) = 0 \quad (2.15a)$$

$$\frac{4kv_{max}\tau_1}{f_{rupt}} \left(1 - \frac{f_{rupt}}{2f_{stall}} \times \left(\frac{\rho_d}{\rho_a}\right)_c\right) = \left(1 + \frac{kv_{max}\tau_1}{f_{rupt}}\right)^2 \quad (2.15b)$$

$$1 - \frac{f_{rupt}}{2f_{stall}} \times \left(\frac{\rho_d}{\rho_a}\right)_c = \frac{f_{rupt}}{4kv_{max}\tau_1} \left(1 + \frac{kv_{max}\tau_1}{f_{rupt}}\right)^2 \quad (2.15c)$$

$$\frac{f_{rupt}}{2f_{stall}} \times \left(\frac{\rho_d}{\rho_a}\right)_c = 1 - \frac{f_{rupt}}{4kv_{max}\tau_1} \left(1 + \frac{kv_{max}\tau_1}{f_{rupt}}\right)^2 \quad (2.15d)$$

$$\boxed{\left(\frac{\rho_d}{\rho_a}\right)_c = \frac{2f_{stall}}{f_{rupt}} \left(1 - \frac{f_{rupt}}{4kv_{max}\tau_1} \left(1 + \frac{kv_{max}\tau_1}{f_{rupt}}\right)^2\right)} \quad (2.15e)$$

$$R_c = \left(\frac{\rho_a}{\rho_a + \rho_d}\right)_c \quad (2.15f)$$

$$\boxed{= \frac{1}{1 + \left(\frac{\rho_d}{\rho_a}\right)_c}} \quad (2.15g)$$

The critical active motor ratio, R_c , for the continuous transition is illustrated in Figure 2.16 and derived in Equation (2.16). Here, R represents the active motor ratio.

Figure 2.16: Continuous case

Injecting $v = 0$ and $f_{imp} = f_{stall}$ into Equation (2.12b)

$$f_{stall} = \left(\frac{\rho_d}{\rho_a}\right)_c \times \frac{f_{rupt}}{2\left(1 - \frac{k \times 0 \times \tau_1}{f_{rupt}}\right)} \quad (2.16a)$$

$$\left(\frac{\rho_d}{\rho_a}\right)_c = \frac{2f_{stall}}{f_{rupt}} \quad (2.16b)$$

$$R_c = \frac{1}{1 + \left(\frac{\rho_d}{\rho_a}\right)_c} \therefore R = \frac{\rho_a / \rho_a}{\rho_a / \rho_a + \rho_d / \rho_a} \quad (2.16c)$$

2.4 Actin Under External Force: 2D Simulation

This section focuses on the method used to reproduce the effects of external forces on the actin filament as observed in the experiments [61] [62]. This was done by adapting the simulation method explained in Section 2.2 and incorporating the application of an external force. Figure 2.17 illustrates how the simulation was set up to exert an external force field on the actin filament as it moves in an in silico motility assay. Two kinds of external force fields were applied. First, the positive force field $F(+)$, and secondly, the negative force field $F(-)$. The positive force field was towards the movement direction of the actin filament v , while the negative force field was towards the opposite direction. The results of this simulation are as explained in Section 3.3.

Figure 2.17: Applying external force field

2.5 Path Persistence Length Calculation

The path persistence length L_p of a filament can be defined as the average length over which the trajectory of the filament remains straight. The persistence length of the actin filament was calculated as in Equation (2.17). In Figure 2.18 the dashed line represents the exact actin leading tip trajectory plotted from the simulation conformation output data points. The single lines (blue) joined with circles represent the approximate trajectory that can be easily predicted to predict where the actin filament is going. The approximate trajectory is the one used during the L_p calculation. The length of a single segment of the approximate actin filament trajectory (the length of line b_1, b_2, \dots) can be varied by varying the Δt of the simulation data points to be used in the analysis. Taking a step size of 0 involves calculating the correlation of b_1 and itself b_1 , that is, the dot product, $U_{b_1} \cdot U_{b_1}$. Taking a step size of 1 means calculating

the correlation of b_1 with b_2 , i.e. $U_{b_1} \cdot U_{b_2}$. Taking a step size of 2 means calculating the correlation of b_1 with b_3 , i.e. $U_{b_1} \cdot U_{b_3}$, and so on. U_{b_l} is a unit vector with the same direction as line b_l , and this continues up to the last line b_l and its unit vector U_{b_l} . To check the straightness of a trajectory, say (x_1, y_1) to (x_3, y_3) , we calculate the angle correlation between b_1 and b_2 by taking a dot product of the two unit vectors, $U_{b_1} \cdot U_{b_2}$. This is as shown in Equation (2.17c), and this correlation is equal to $\cos(\theta)$. If the correlation is 1, the two lines are perfectly aligned to make a straight line. A value such as 0 would indicate no correlation and -1 would indicate an opposite perfect alignment. By comparing the various correlations formed by the actin filament leading tip, we can estimate the actin filament L_p .

Figure 2.18: Actin persistence length

$$\|b_1\| = \sqrt{(x_2 - x_1)^2 + (y_2 - y_1)^2} \tag{2.17a}$$

$$U_{b_1} = \left(\frac{(x_2 - x_1)}{\|b_1\|}, \frac{(y_2 - y_1)}{\|b_1\|} \right) \tag{2.17b}$$

$$\cos(\theta) = U_{b_1} \cdot U_{b_2} \tag{2.17c}$$

To calculate the average correlation, $\langle \cos(\Delta\theta)(s) \rangle$, the Algorithm 6 is used. Δs is the step size taken. For example, if $\Delta s = 1$, the first correlation is calculated by taking the dot product, $U_{b_1} \cdot U_{b_2}$, and if $\Delta s = 2$, the first correlation is obtained by taking $U_{b_1} \cdot U_{b_3}$, and so on. Correlations in all steps are then calculated and then the average

is evaluated in each case.

```

1 for  $\Delta s = 0$  do
2   Calculate  $\langle \cos(\Delta\theta) \rangle_0$ ; // step size = 0
3   = mean $\langle U_{b1} \cdot U_{b(1+0)}, U_{b2} \cdot U_{b(2+0)}, U_{b3} \cdot U_{b(3+0)}, \dots, U_{b(l-0)} \cdot U_{bl} \rangle$ ;
4 for  $\Delta s = 1$  do
5   Calculate  $\langle \cos(\Delta\theta) \rangle_1$ ; // step size = 1
6   = mean $\langle U_{b1} \cdot U_{b(1+1)}, U_{b2} \cdot U_{b(2+1)}, U_{b3} \cdot U_{b(3+1)}, \dots, U_{b(l-1)} \cdot U_{bl} \rangle$ ;
7 for  $\Delta s = 2$  do
8   Calculate  $\langle \cos(\Delta\theta) \rangle_2$ ; // step size = 2
9   = mean $\langle U_{b1} \cdot U_{b(1+2)}, U_{b2} \cdot U_{b(2+2)}, U_{b3} \cdot U_{b(3+2)}, \dots, U_{b(l-2)} \cdot U_{bl} \rangle$ ;
10 :
11 for  $\Delta s = n$  do
12   Calculate  $\langle \cos(\Delta\theta) \rangle_n$ ; // step size = n
13   = mean $\langle U_{b1} \cdot U_{b(1+n)}, U_{b2} \cdot U_{b(2+n)}, U_{b3} \cdot U_{b(3+n)}, \dots, U_{b(l-n)} \cdot U_{bl} \rangle$ ;

```

Algorithm 6: Actin filament trajectory average correlation. This algorithm is implemented in Appendix B.1(line 127-166)

Figure 2.19 shows the expected correlation plot. As the actin filament continues to move, the correlation of the leading tip decays. An implementation of Algorithm 6 and a L_p plot is shown in Appendix B.1.

Figure 2.19: Persistence length example plot

$$S = \Delta s \cdot v \cdot \Delta t \tag{2.18a}$$

$$\langle \cos(\Delta\theta) \rangle = \exp\left(-\frac{S}{2L_p}\right) \tag{2.18b}$$

$$\log \langle \cos(\Delta\theta) \rangle = -\frac{1}{2L_p} \times S \tag{2.18c}$$

As explained in Algorithm 6, $\langle \cos(\Delta\theta) \rangle$ is the average correlation of the actin leading tip trajectory steps, S is the distance covered by the trajectory as in Equation (2.18a), total distance, $S_{total} = n \cdot v \cdot \Delta t$, and L_p is the path persistence length of the trajectory.

As shown in Figure 2.19, L_p of the actin filament, L_p , can be calculated by calculating the gradient $(\frac{\Delta y}{\Delta x})$ of the line of best fit of Figure 2.19(right) and equating this gradient with $-\frac{1}{2L_p}$ of Equation (2.18c). Equation (2.18b) is derived from Jonathon Howard book [11] in pg. 111. When taking $\log\langle \cos(\Delta\theta) \rangle$, about 10% of the data may be used since as noticed in Algorithm 6, since a large step size is taken as n is approached, few data points are available towards the end of the trajectory thus losing statistical significance.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

“The complexity of the protein-surface systems is greatly amplified by the polymer-fluid interface and the structure of molecular motors, making the study of these interactions critical to the success of molecular motor-based nanodevices.”

Biosensors and Bioelectronics
KRISTI L. HANSON *et al.*, 2017

3.1	Actin over Active and Defective Myosin: 3D Simulation	42
3.1.1	Actin Conformation and Trajectory	42
3.1.2	Actin Filament Speed	46
3.1.3	Actin Filament Path Persistence Length	49
3.1.4	Myosin Binding to the Actin	52
3.1.5	Myosin Lifetime	61
3.2	Actin over Active and Defective Myosin: 1D Mathematical Model	64
3.2.1	Model Predictions	64
3.2.2	Model Applications	66
3.3	Actin under External Force: 2D Simulation	69
3.3.1	Effect on the Trajectories	69
3.3.2	Effect on Speed	71
3.3.3	Path Persistence Length	71
3.3.4	Biosensor Design Insight	76
3.4	Recommendations	77

In this chapter, the results for the three main projects are presented and discussed. These results include the 3D simulation of an actin filament propelled by myosin motors, the 1D mathematical model that describes the movement of the actin filament

over defective myosin, and the movement of the actin filament under the influence of the external force field.

3.1 Actin over Active and Defective Myosin: 3D Simulation

In this section, the results of the actin-myosin 3D simulation are discussed in detail. The implications of these results are revealed along with the presentation of the results.

3.1.1 Actin Conformation and Trajectory

Figure 3.1: Actin filament conformation changes for various active motor ratios, $r_{substrate}$. $3\mu m$ actin filament, $ATP = 2000 \mu M$, and motor density = $3000 \mu m^{-2}$. (a) $r_{substrate} = 0.70$, (b) $r_{substrate} = 0.90$, (c) $r_{substrate} = 0.94$, (d) $r_{substrate} = 0.98$. A video of this movement is available [63].

Actin Filament Conformation

Figure 3.1 shows the conformation of a $3\mu m$ actin filament that moves over active and defective myosins, as the active myosin ratio is systematically varied from $r_{substrate} = 0.1$ to $r_{substrate} = 1.0$. This movement of the actin filament undergoes three phases, hereafter referred to as the initiation phase (Figure 3.1(a)), the transition phase (Figure 3.1(b),(c)), and the gliding phase (Figure 3.1(d)). The initiation phase occurs at $r_{substrate} = 0.1$ to $r_{substrate} \leq 0.9$, where the actin filament remains stuck in approximately the same initial conformation throughout the simulation time. In the transition phase $0.9 < r_{substrate} \leq 0.92$, the actin filament wiggles around and occasionally makes jerky movements. These movements may eventually result in a progressive forward or curly movement. At $r_{substrate} > 0.92$, the actin filament enters the glide phase, which exhibits a continuous smooth procession. These changes are reminiscent of the microtubule movements discussed by Scharrel *et al.* [64].

By observing the position changes of the leading tip, we can have a bird's eye perspective of the whole actin filament translation. These changes in the trajectory

of the filament can be used to estimate the relative distance travelled by actin as seen in Figure 3.2. In this study, the average speed of the actin filament and its L_p were calculated from the data from the trajectory of the tip. This comes in handy in predicting the performance of molecular shuttles in a biosensor application.

Figure 3.2: Actin filament trajectory

Actin Filament Initiation Phase

In the initiation phase, the relative movement of the actin filament is negligible. As seen in Figure 3.1(a) and Figure 3.2 ($r_{\text{substrate}} = 0.90$), the actin filament is relatively straight throughout the simulation and the trajectory of the leading tip does not show progressive movement. Most defective myosins bind to the actin filament, since the active myosin ratio of the motility assay is the lowest at this stage. Although the middle part of the actin filament remains relatively straight with minimal fluctuations around the same position, the tip and tail segments exhibit more fluctuations. Although defective myosin binds throughout the length of the actin filament, the middle segments are coupled with other segments, damping down some fluctuations, whereas the leading and trailing tips are more exposed to the Brownian effects and thus fluctuating more.

Actin Filament Transition Phase

During the transition phase, the actin filament may conform to a variety of shapes, but the spiral shape is the most prevalent. Figure 3.3 shows typical screenshots of the movements of the actin filament during the transition phase. The leading tip of the actin filament may be captured, whereas the middle part and the trailing end continue to move. This portrays movements similar to the spiral defects described by *Bourdieu*

et al. [65] and may serve to explain the mechanism of spiral defects and the resistance to smooth glide.

Figure 3.3: Spiral defects. Transition phase movements at $r_{substrate} = 0.92$, $3\mu m$ actin filament, ATP = $2000\mu M$, and motor density = $2000\mu m^{-2}$

The mechanism of spiral movement of the actin filament during the transition phase may be attributed to its inherent structure. The structure of the actin filament is analogous to that of a mechanical chain. The flexural rigidity of the actin filament is such that it is easier to pull the entire filament than to push it. This asymmetry of forces creates a push-the-tail bias, a phenomenon that makes it easier to slide the actin tail and detach a defective myosin attached close to the trailing end than the one attached close to the leading tip. This promotes buckling, and hence curling, starting from the leading segment. This kind of asymmetry of forces has also been observed by *Koenderink et al.* [66], [67]. Figure 3.4 shows the simulation instances captured during the transition phase. If a point in the leading segment of the actin filament is caught by defective myosin, only that segment stays stuck, and its movement is inhibited. When the leading segment is stuck, the middle and tail segments continue to move. This is because it takes more time for the current detachment force to build up to the set critical detachment force (9.2 pN) that can remove the attached defective myosin. Before this force adds up, time elapses, and more defective myosins are still likely to bind to the stuck segment, holding it immobile for even longer. The transition phase trajectories seen in Figure 3.2 ($r_{substrate} = 0.92$) are short due to defective myosins that still inhibit progressive glide, thus the short distance travelled. Inhibition of the relative movement of the actin filament is similar to inhibition of the movement of the actin filament by Calponin discussed by *Shirinsky et al.* [68]. Every defective myosin that binds to the actin filament segment slows that segment and, eventually, the entire movement of the actin filament.

Figure 3.4: Push-pull force asymmetry at $r_{substrate} = 0.90$. Red line with red circles: the actin filament. Green dots: binding active myosins, Blue dots: binding defective myosin

Actin Filament Smooth Gliding

The movement of the actin filament on a motility assay rich in active myosin constitutes a smooth glide. Figure 3.1(d) and Figure 3.2 ($r_{substrate} \geq 0.96$) shows the smooth glide phase where the actin filament covers the longest distance. The distance travelled by the actin filament increases drastically with the high active myosin ratio of the motility assay. This shows that purification of the actin-myosin motility assay is important in reducing surface-adsorbed myosins that can inhibit movement. Although the effect of this process on actin speed may be unpredictable [48], affinity purification has been shown to improve motility [69]. To achieve smooth sliding of the actin filament, a sufficient composition of active myosin is essential in the motility assay. In our simulation, a composition of $\geq 10\%$ defective myosin was found to compromise motility and stop movement of the actin filament. Because defective myosins do not hydrolyse ATP, they bind permanently to the actin filament until they are forced to detach with greater force. Active myosins hydrolyse ATP and can collectively produce the impetus to cause bound defective myosins to detach from the actin filament. Reducing the defective myosin population to $< 10\%$ causes the glide of the actin filament to begin.

Actin Filament Path Persistence Length

The persistence length⁴ of a filament trajectory is the average length at which the trajectory remains straight. Knowledge of persistence length is helpful for gauging the ability to control the filament when designing biosensor guiding tracks. To calculate the persistence length of the actin filament trajectories, we adopted previously published methods [52], [70], and [11], as illustrated in Figure 2.18 in Section 2.5, in the methodology chapter.

3.1.2 Actin Filament Speed

Since the movement of the actin filament is stochastic, to calculate the velocity that captures the general direction of the actin filament, we need to choose an appropriate change in time Δt . In Figure 3.5, when choosing various Δt , the trajectory of the actin tip varies. Using a small resolution, say $\Delta t = 0.01$, shows a very random trajectory of the actin tip. There are two problems that arise when we use this small Δt . First, it is difficult to predict where the actin filament is going, as the actin tip seems to drift in all directions. Second, calculating the speed using this small Δt will result in a rather high actin filament speed, characterised by high deviations, which is unrealistic.

Figure 3.5: Various tip trajectories based on Δt variation.

Figure 3.6 shows various speed calculation results when various Δt are chosen. Around $\Delta t = 0.07$, the speed and deviations of the actin filament seem to settle, and the speed of the actin filament is approximately the same. In this study, we chose

$\Delta t = 0.01$ since at this point the actin filament speed is already settled and in our 5 s simulation, there are still enough data points to calculate the average speed.

Figure 3.6: Δt used while calculating speed. The error bars here and after represent the standard deviation.

Figure 3.7 shows the velocity of various actin filaments. Here, all parameters were kept constant, but the seed to generate random numbers was changed to simulate various actin filaments. When the random seed of simulation is varied, new actin filaments can be simulated. Various actin filament velocities were observed to be on average approximately the same. All filaments show a speed of approximately $0 \mu\text{m/s}$ in the initiation stage. The speed starts to increase in the transition / intermediate stage, and there is smooth movement in the smooth glide stage, where the speed remains high ($\approx 3 - 7 \mu\text{m/sec}$). Overall, we observed that a high active ratio is required to achieve and maintain a smooth glide of the actin filament. There is a sharp transition between the initiation speed and the smooth glide speed. This implies that the removal of nonfunctional denatured myosin motors will contribute to smooth glide of the actin filament; otherwise, the presence of denatured/defective myosin in the motility assay will cause the actin filament to come to a grinding halt.

Figure 3.7: Actin filament speed from various filaments.

The gliding onset of the actin filament remains unchanged despite changes in parameters such as motor density, ATP concentration, and actin filament length. Figure 3.8 (a) shows a graph of two actin filament speeds: one at a motor density of $2000 \mu\text{m}^{-2}$ and the other at a motor density of $3000 \mu\text{m}^{-2}$. This difference in motor density does not translate into a significant difference in actin filament speed. In Figure 3.8(b), a low ATP concentration ($500 \mu\text{M}$) produces a slower actin filament speed, but the gliding initiation position remains the same ($r_{\text{substrate}} \approx 0.92$). Similar results are obtained when different actin lengths are used, as shown in Figure 3.8(c). For actin filaments $2 \mu\text{m}$ and $3 \mu\text{m}$, the speed remains the same and the gliding onset is still in the same position. In the simulations in Figure 3.8, the active ratio of the motility assay is the only factor that influences the initiation of gliding of the actin filament.

Figure 3.8: Red: AF speed for AF = $3 \mu\text{m}$, ATP = $2000 \mu\text{M}$, MD = $3000 \mu\text{m}^{-2}$. Blue: (a) MD dependence AF = $3 \mu\text{m}$, ATP = $2000 \mu\text{M}$, MD = $2000 \mu\text{m}^{-2}$ (b) ATP dependence AF = $3 \mu\text{m}$, ATP = $500 \mu\text{M}$, MD = $3000 \mu\text{m}^{-2}$ (c) length dependence AF = $2 \mu\text{m}$, ATP = $2000 \mu\text{M}$, MD = $3000 \mu\text{m}^{-2}$

In our simulation, we found that the speed of the actin filament is markedly influenced by the set detachment force of the defective myosin. In Figure 3.9, the initiation of glide of the actin filament varies depending on the set detachment force. For the detachment force of 9.2 pN, the onset of glide is at $r_{substrate} = 0.9$. For lower detachment forces of 6.9 pN and 4.6 pN, the initiation of the glide started at $r_{substrate} = 0.8$ and $r_{substrate} = 0.4$, respectively. This effect is similar to that of the load-dependence force-velocity relation studied by others [71], [72]. The higher the load on myosin, the slower the actin filament moves. Here, the set detachment force is directly proportional to the onset of the gliding. Reducing the detachment force by half from 9.2 pN to 4.6 pN reduces the gliding onset from 0.9 to 0.4, which is close to half. This implies that the onset of glide of the actin filament can be improved by making defective myosins dissociate faster. A method such as that studied by Shen *et al.* [73] may serve to improve the speed of the actin filament.

Figure 3.9: Actin speed with various detachment forces. Red: detachforce = 9.2 pN, Lime: detachment force = 6.9 pN, Grey: detachment force = 4.6 pN.

3.1.3 Actin Filament Path Persistence Length

The trajectory plot of Figure 3.10 shows the trajectories of seven actin filaments as the value of $r_{substrate}$ is systematically reduced. The original $\Delta t = 0.01$ of the simulation output is used to make this graph. However, as explained in Section 3.3.3, $\Delta t = 0.2$ and 30% of the data are used during the calculation of L_p .

Figure 3.10: Seven actin filament trajectories. From left to right, $r_{substrate} = [1.00, 0.98, 0.96, 0.94]$.

Figure 3.11: Actin filament L_p at $r_{substrate} = 1.00$

Figure 3.12: Actin filament L_p at $r_{\text{substrate}} = 0.98$

Figure 3.13: Actin filament L_p at $r_{\text{substrate}} = 0.96$

Figure 3.14: Actin filament L_p at $r_{\text{substrate}} = 0.94$

Figure 3.15 shows changes in the average L_p as the active motor ratio, $r_{\text{substrate}}$, increases from the continuous glide threshold of 0.94 to 1.00. It can be deduced that as $r_{\text{substrate}}$ increases, the actin filament L_p improves from $2.2 \mu\text{m}$ to $4.6 \mu\text{m}$. This may be attributed to the high speed of the actin filament with more active motors, which tends to translate the actin filament with fewer wiggling effects.

Figure 3.15: Actin filament L_p changes as $r_{\text{substrate}}$ increases.

3.1.4 Myosin Binding to the Actin

In this section, binding changes in the in silico motility assay are discussed. Speed changes are also discussed in relation to myosin binding changes.

Binding Changes

To further probe the onset of glide, we plotted the instantaneous binding of myosin to the actin filament as a function of time. As seen in Figure 3.16, the binding myosin behaviour can still be described in three phases. During the initiation phase, defective binding myosins increase rapidly, fluctuate less, and are much more abundant than active myosins. Active binding myosins in this phase fluctuate, but generally stay much lower than that of defective myosin binding. In the transition phase, the binding active myosins generally exceed the binding defective myosins, but there are some instances in which the latter might exceed the former. The number of defective and active myosins bound in this phase fluctuates more than in any other phase. In the glide phase, the binding active myosins are always more binding defective myosins. From this observation, it can be deduced that, for the actin filament to glide, the number of active myosin bindings to the actin filament must exceed that of the binding defective myosin.

Figure 3.16: Instantaneous binding myosins. $ATP = 2000 \mu M$, and motor density = $3000 \mu m^{-2}$

Figure 3.17 shows the average binding myosin in each segment of an actin filament during a 5-second simulation. During the initiation phase, defective myosins that bind to all segments of the actin filament are more common than active myosins. The binding pattern is generally random along the actin filament segments. During the transition phase, the number of defective myosins that bind to every segment is generally less than the number of active myosins. Interestingly, in the transition phase, while the active myosins binding to the segments of the actin filament remain relatively the same, the defective myosins binding to the leading segments are more than the myosins binding around the middle and tail segments of the actin filament. This reinforces the previous discussion of Figure 3.3 and Figure 3.4. In the smooth gliding phase, the defective myosin binding to the actin filament in every segment is lower than that of the active binding myosin, and the segment distribution is uniform.

As long as defective myosins that adhere to the actin filament in every segment are more common than active myosins, glide will not occur. Any segment will tend to move whenever the binding active myosins exceed the binding defective myosins.

Figure 3.17: Mean binding myosins in each segment of the actin filament.

Binding Myosin and Speed

To understand the relationship between binding myosin and the speed produced by the moving actin filament, we examine these quantities side by side. In our simulation, the introduction of defective myosin into the in vitro motility assay hampers motility almost completely. As seen in Figure 3.18 (left), the actomyosin assay containing defective myosin $\geq 10\%$ does not translate the actin filament. At this point, the actin filament speed is $\approx 0 \mu\text{m}/\text{s}$ and the active binding myosins are much lower than the defective binding myosins (Figure 3.18 (middle)). From the onset of glide ($r_{\text{substrate}} \approx 0.92$), the minimum procession speed was observed to be $0.2 \pm 0.75 \mu\text{m}/\text{sec}$. Active binding myosins are ≈ 50 , while defective binding myosins are half that of active myosins, ≈ 25 . The maximum speed was observed to be $7.25 \pm 0.75 \mu\text{m}/\text{sec}$ during a smooth glide. The smooth glide speed of $7 \mu\text{m}/\text{sec}$ is much higher than that achieved in experiments such as *Hanson et al.* [74]. However, this discrepancy may be explained by a difference in temperature when performing an experiment [75]. Furthermore, in an experiment to investigate the motion of F-Actin and its attachment to surfaces, Fig. 5 of *Winkelmann et al.* [76] shows how various temperatures can influence the velocity of the actin filament. In all phases, except at $r_{\text{substrate}} = 1.0$, the ratio of active myosin binding to the actin filament is much lower than the active myosins available in the motility assay (Figure 3.18 (right), Figure 3.21).

Figure 3.18: Actin speed and binding myosin changes. (a) AF speed changes with increase in active myosin ratio, (b) binding active (green) and binding defective (blue) myosin number, (c) changes in active binding ratio

To determine how binding myosins change when subjected to different conditions, we simulated the actin filament under different motor densities and ATP concentration. Figures 3.19 and Figure 3.20 show how the speed of the actin filament and the associated binding motor change when the actin filament is subjected to a lower myosin density of $2000 \mu m^{-2}$ and a lower ATP of $500 \mu M$, respectively. The speed of the actin filament is similar to that of the previous higher myosin density of $3000 \mu m^{-2}$. However, the average number of myosin binding to the actin filament is lower for the motor density of $2000 \mu m^{-2}$. At $r_{substrate} = 1.00$ and at a myosin density of $2000 \mu m^{-2}$, the average number of myosin binding to actin is the lowest and, as a result, the actin filament is more likely to detach at a motor density of $2000 \mu m^{-2}$ than at a motor density of $3000 \mu m^{-2}$.

Figure 3.19: Actin speed and binding myosin changes at MD 2000.

Figure 3.20: Actin speed and binding myosin changes at ATP 500.

Figure 3.21: Binding myosin, binding ratio, lifetime comparison. Motor density = $3000\mu\text{m}^{-2}$, ATP = $2000\mu\text{M}$

The actin speed and the trend of the binding ratio remain the same, except for ATP $500\mu\text{M}$, where the speed is significantly lower. For both $2000\mu\text{M}$ and $500\mu\text{M}$, the average number of myosins binding to the actin filament remains the same until the start of smooth glide of the actin filament. At this point, the number of binding myosins for $500\mu\text{M}$ is greater than that for $2000\mu\text{M}$. The increase in the number of active myosins binding at low ATP is plausible due to the dependence of myosins on ATP, as discussed in *Lynn et al.* [77]. Since myosin can bind to the actin filament or ATP [78], when there is a deficiency in ATP, more myosin will remain bound to the actin filament.

The amount of force required to detach a defective myosin influences the number of active myosins that adhere to the actin filament. In Figure 3.22, various detachment forces for defective myosin were used (4.6 pN, 6.9 pN and 9.2 pN), while the detachment force for active myosin remained the same in all simulations (9.2 pN). For the defective detachment force of 4.6 pN, 6.9 pN, and 9.2 pN, the number of myosin binding activity increases linearly until the onset of glide of $r_{\text{substrate}} = 0.4$, $r_{\text{substrate}} = 0.8$, and $r_{\text{substrate}} = 0.9$, respectively (Figure 3.22(a)). At higher detachment forces of the defective myosin, a higher active ratio is required for the motility assay to have a higher active ratio, and for the movement of the actin filament, a higher active binding ratio is required. The binding ratio of active myosins to actin filament improves as the detachment force of defective myosin is reduced (Figure 3.22(b)). This finding

is similar to the behaviour observed by *Cheng et al.*[71]. Defective myosin increases the load on myosin, and more myosins are required to bind to the actin filament to overcome this resistance.

Figure 3.22: Binding myosins and the ratio of various defective myosin detachment forces. Red:detach force = 9.2 pN, Lime: detach force = 6.9 pN, Grey: detach force = 4.6 pN. **(a)** active binding motors with various detachment forces, **(b)** active binding ratio with various detachment forces.

To elucidate the relationship between actin filament speed and binding myosin, we examined the correlation between these parameters. As seen in Figure 3.23, the number of defective myosins binding to the actin filament is highly correlated with the number of active myosins binding to the actin filament. The defective motors were modelled to stick to the actin filament once they were bound, unless overcome by a higher force. Active myosins bind and unbind according to the hydrolysis cycle. When the binding defective myosin increases, the load on the myosin increases, and the number of binding active myosins also increases. It is plausible that the number of active myosins binding to the actin filament increases/readjusts to counter the load and thus tends to favour ADP release, and hence, active myosins stay bound to the actin filament for a longer time.

Figure 3.23: Correlation between binding defective and active myosin. (a) $r_{substrate} = 0.90$, (b) $r_{substrate} = 0.92$, (c) $r_{substrate} = 0.94$. ATP = 2000 μM , and motor density = 3000 μm^{-2}

Next, we checked the correlation between the binding of active myosin and the speed of the actin filament. In Figure 3.24, there is no correlation between the number of active myosin binding and the speed. The speed of the actin filament does not necessarily increase with increasing number of binding myosins. As explained in Figure 3.23, the dramatic increase in active myosin binding occurs when the actin filament becomes stuck due to the accumulation of defective myosin, and then active myosin increases to counteract stall. Once the stall has been overcome, the speed of the actin filament does not increase. This implies that the increase in the speed of the glide of the actin filament is not related to an increase in binding active myosin and vice versa. However, as observed in the correlation between the ratio of active myosin binding and the speed of the actin filament in Figure 3.25, there is a faint correlation between the ratio of active myosin binding and the increase in speed at the beginning of glide ($r_{substrate} \approx 0.92$). This suggests that increasing the number of active myosins that adhere to the actin filament during the onset of glide increases the speed.

Figure 3.24: Correlation between binding active myosin and actin filament speed. (a) $r_{substrate} = 0.90$, (b) $r_{substrate} = 0.92$, (c) $r_{substrate} = 0.94$. ATP = 2000 μM , and motor density = 3000 μm^{-2}

Figure 3.25: Correlation between the ratio of binding active myosin and the actin filament speed. (a) $r_{substrate} = 0.90$, (b) $r_{substrate} = 0.92$, (c) $r_{substrate} = 0.94$. ATP = 2000 μM , and motor density = 3000 μm^{-2}

To check whether the number of myosins bound in the simulation is probable, we calculated the number of defective myosins that can bind to the actin filament. The number of defective myosins bound was selected for simplicity. Figure 3.26 shows an actin filament surrounded by randomly distributed myosin motors.

$$Binding\ myosins = (1 - r_{substrate}) \times \rho \times L_{AF} \times 2w, \tag{3.1a}$$

where

- $r_{substrate}$: Active motor ratio
- L_{AF} : Length of actin filament
- ρ : Myosins density
- w : Distance within which myosin can bind to actin

Figure 3.26: Possible number myosins that can bind to the actin filament. Red: actin filament, Green dot: myosin

To estimate the lifetime of binding, the fraction of time that a defective myosin stays attached to the actin filament, it is assumed that the defective motor undergoes a

repeated cycle of binding and unbinding:

$$T_{off} = \frac{1}{ka} \tag{3.2a}$$

$$kVT_{on} = Fd; T_{on} = \frac{Fd}{kV} \tag{3.2b}$$

$$\frac{T_{on}}{T_{on} + T_{off}} = \frac{\frac{Fd}{kV}}{\frac{Fd}{kV} + \frac{1}{ka}} \tag{3.2c}$$

$$= \frac{Fd}{Fd + \frac{kV}{ka}} \tag{3.2d}$$

Defective binding myosin can be expressed as:

$$\frac{Fd}{(Fd) + (kV/ka)} \times (1 - r_{substrate}) \times \rho \times L_{AF} \times 2(Fd/k), \tag{3.3}$$

Figure 3.27: Estimating time taken by a defective myosin to stay bound to the actin filament.

where

ka : Binding rate

k : Spring constant

Fd : Detachment force

V : Gliding speed of the actin filament

Figure 3.28 shows the fit between the simulation output and the estimate of Equation (3.3). The results of independent mathematical calculations fit well with the simulation results. This estimation formula does not apply to the binding of active myosin to the actin filament, since more complex factors such as the hydrolysis cycle have to be taken into consideration.

Figure 3.28: Predicting binding defective myosin. Blue: simulation, Black: Equation (3.3).

3.1.5 Myosin Lifetime

Figure 3.29 shows the average time myosin remains bound to the actin filament, hereafter referred to as lifetime. The lifetime of active and defective myosin binding generally decreases as the active myosin ratio of the motility assay gradually increases from 0.7 to 1.0. For active myosin, the lifetime is longer in the initiation phase and shorter in the glide phase. In the initiation phase, the load on the active myosin is larger due to the presence of binding defective myosins that remain stuck to the actin filament for an average time of around 4.4 seconds, almost throughout the 5 seconds of simulation. At the same time, active myosin binds to the actin filament for a period of a little more than 0.012 seconds. This load encourages the release of ADP and hence facilitates binding. Several defective myosins bind to the actin filament without detaching, causing the actin filament to stay in situ. The load on myosin gradually eases during the transition phase and is lowest during the glide phase. The lifetime of the binding myosin adjusts according to the applied force and this is consistent with the load dependence described by *Veigel et al.* [72], [79], [80]. The lifetime of defective myosin shown in Figure 3.29 (right) is much longer in the initiation phase and rapidly decreases to ≈ 0 during the glide phase. This underpins the importance of the purification techniques of the motility test discussed by *Kron et al.* [69].

Figure 3.30 shows the lifetime of defective myosin in detail. As $r_{substrate}$ is reduced below the gliding outset, the lifetime of the defective myosin increases as the simulation time increases. Therefore, the defective lifetime tends to infinity as the simulation time increases, similar to Equation (3.4). To validate the results, the red dot dotted line in Figure 3.30(right) uses Equation (3.2b) and the speed of the actin filament to estimate the lifetime of the defective myosin. The trend of the estimated life is similar to the simulated lifetime.

$$\lim_{\tau_{simulation} \rightarrow \infty} \tau_{life} \approx \infty \quad (3.4)$$

Figure 3.29: Comparing myosin lifetimes. Green: active myosin, Blue: defective myosin.

Figure 3.30: The defective myosin lifetime during continuous gliding. The estimate was done using Equation (3.2b).

Figure 3.31 shows the lifetime distribution of active and defective binding myosins, respectively. On the one hand, the lifetime of the binding active myosins follows the Poisson distribution because the binding behaviour is independent and the binding rate is constant. On the other hand, the lifetime distribution of defective binding myosin is random during the initiation phase and changes to Poisson during the glide phase. This suggests that smooth glide is preferred when various defective myosins do not bind to the actin filament at the same time. Continuous glide could also be favoured when the lifetime of defective myosin binding is reduced. This may be achieved by increasing the ionic strength of the buffer.

Figure 3.31: **(a)** Lifetime histogram for binding active motors. **(b)** Lifetime histogram for binding defective motors

To further investigate the phenomenon of myosin load dependence, we checked the lifetime of active myosin with and without the load dependence function. In Figure 3.32, the lifetime of the active myosin binding remained the lowest ($\approx 0.003 \text{ sec.}$) when the simulation was done without the load-dependence function. This justifies that the longer lifetime recorded by active myosins during the initiation phase is due to the contribution of the load-dependence Equation (2.8).

Figure 3.32: Green: active binding myosin with load dependence, grey: active binding myosin without load dependence. Assay active ratio = $r_{substrate}$. The active myosin lifetime data is from another set of simulation similar to Figure 3.29(left)

Figure 3.33 shows the lifetime of active binding myosin under different defective

detachment force conditions. Before the load caused by the binding defective myosin is overcome, the lifetime of the active motor remains the highest (0.011 sec.).

Figure 3.33: Comparing lifetime in various defective myosin detachment force conditions. Red: detachment force = 9.2 pN, Lime: detachment force = 6.9 pN, Grey: detachment force = 4.6 pN, Blue: without load dependence function

3.2 Actin over Active and Defective Myosin: 1D Mathematical Model

In this section, the results of the 1D mathematical model are discussed in detail, in connection to the 3D simulation above.

3.2.1 Model Predictions

Figure 3.34 shows the possible solutions for the velocity given the various forces applied in our mathematical model.

Figure 3.34: Model possible solutions for myosin

From the schematic of Figure 3.35, which is based on the mathematical models derived in Section 2.3, stationary to mobile prediction can be obtained from the

intersection of the force-velocity and impedance (active ratio) plots. In Figure 3.35 (left), at the stationary point, the red impedance graph #4 (obtained from Equation (2.12b)) intersects the blue force-velocity graph (obtained from Equation (2.10)) at $v = 0 \mu m/s$. The impedance plot #3 has only one speed solution (one intersection). From the impedance plots between #3 and #2 there are two solutions. The impedance plots around #1 have one high-speed solution. This shows a discontinuous stationary-motile transition of actin-based molecular shuttles, as seen in Figure 3.35(right). The slope of the force-velocity graph is mostly steeper than that of the impedance graph, that is, the ratio $\frac{-k\tau_1 v_{max}}{2f_{rupt}} > 1$. Therefore, the angle of slope at the intersection of these graphs can be used to describe the stationary to motile transition of actin filaments. Depending on the active ratio of myosin motors, the motility of the actin-based molecular shuttle makes sharp transitions from stationary to motile, compared to the molecular shuttles based on microtubules [81]. This model can be applied to microtubule-based molecular shuttles to elucidate motility.

Figure 3.35: Model prediction schematic. Red: active ratio (representing impedance), Blue: force-velocity relationship

For the case of $\frac{-k\tau_1 v_{max}}{2f_{rupt}} > 1$, the three cases described above can be summarised as follows. In the first case, $\frac{\rho_d}{\rho_a}$ is small and the red curve #1 of Figure 3.35(left) has one intersection that gives one solution equal to the positive solution of Equation (2.13e). In the second case, the red curve #2 intersects the blue force-velocity line at two points, providing two solutions of Equation (2.13e). In the third case, the red curve #4 does not intersect the force-velocity line and there is no motile solution.

Figure 3.36: Stability of the solutions

In the mathematical model, we solved for an active ratio of 0.8 to 0.9. The blue line of Figure 3.36 represents the speed, and the red line of Figure 3.36 represents the impedance. There are three cases of solutions to this mathematical model. In the first case, the impedance is above the critical value and there is no motile solution. In the second case, the impedance is at the critical value, and there is only one motile solution. In the third case, there are two motile solutions, but only one is stable. When the low-speed solution is considered, if the actin filament fluctuations cause its speed to increase, as shown in the figure, the impedance reduces, causing the actin filament speed to accelerate even further to a higher speed. The filament does not return to its original speed, which means that it is unstable. With a high-speed solution, if the speed of the actin filament increases as a result of thermal fluctuations, the corresponding impedance increases, and the actin filament speed decelerates back to its original speed. Therefore, this speed is stable.

3.2.2 Model Applications

In the 1D mathematical model, the active ratio $r_{substrate}$ emerges as the singularly pivotal factor influencing both the onset of actin filament glide and its speed. Maintaining an active ratio exceeding 80% proves imperative for sustaining continuous glide movement of the actin filament. Remarkably, the outcomes derived from the 1D mathematical model mirror those obtained from the 3D simulation discussed earlier.

When scrutinizing the gliding speed of cytoskeletal filaments, two distinct solutions manifest at intermediate ρ_d/ρ_a values. Solution Figure 3.36(a) demonstrates stability, whereas solution Figure 3.36(b) depicts instability. Fluctuations in gliding speed around the higher-speed solution Figure 3.36(a) are contemplated. The cytoskeletal filament's velocity may intermittently surge or dwindle around its mean value. For the high-speed solution Figure 3.36(a), an upsurge in filament velocity yields greater impedance, consequently decelerating back to the initial gliding speed. Conversely, a decrease in filament velocity triggers diminished impedance, thereby accelerating back to the initial speed. Thus, the high-speed solution exhibits stability. Conversely, the low-speed solution (Figure 3.36(b)) proves unstable, as any rise in

filament speed catalyzes further acceleration, exacerbating fluctuations.

Stable solutions render the gliding speed as a function of ρ_d/ρ_a or r . Intriguingly, the gliding speed remains independent of filament length, with ρ_d/ρ_a standing as the solitary parameter dictating speed. The continuity of the stationary-motile transition profoundly impacts cytoskeletal filaments near the critical ratio. Experimental disparities in the densities of active and defective biomolecular motors engender motility variations within filaments. Certain segments may exhibit marginally lower ρ_d/ρ_a values, propelling them, while other regions with slightly higher ratios remain stationary. This motility heterogeneity may instigate undulation and even filament rupture.

These insights are further elucidated by referring to Figures 3.37, which depict plots of gliding speed, v , as a function of impedance for microtubule-based molecular shuttles. The red curves delineate various active motor ratios, r , while the blue line signifies the $f - v$ relation. The critical active motor ratio in this context stands at 0.372, illustrating how the gliding speed fluctuates with impedance across different ratios.

Figure 3.37: Prediction of changes in active ratios of vs. $f - v$ relationship of kinesin.

Figure 3.38 and Figure 3.39 illustrate the distinctions in gliding onset between the actin filament and the microtubule filament, as predicted by our mathematical model solutions. Specifically, the actin filament necessitates a relatively high active ratio of myosins compared to the active ratio of kinesins required by the microtubule for the initiation of gliding movement. However, once the gliding commences, actin filaments achieve significantly higher velocities than microtubules.

Expanding upon this observation, it becomes evident that the dynamics of actin filaments and microtubules under external forces are intricately governed by the interplay between motor proteins and filament properties. The higher active ratio requirement for actin filaments suggests a greater reliance on myosin activity to overcome impediments and initiate movement compared to microtubules and kinesins. However, the subsequent enhancement in velocity achieved by actin filaments underscores their superior efficiency and effectiveness in cargo transport and cellular processes.

Moreover, these findings underscore the utility and versatility of simple mathematical models in elucidating complex biological phenomena and guiding experimental design and interpretation. By capturing the approximate underlying principles governing filament dynamics, simple models empower researchers to predict and understand the behaviour of cellular components under various conditions, offering valuable insights for biomedical applications.

Figure 3.38: The predicted speed of the actin filament.

Figure 3.39: Kinesin speed prediction for the mathematical model.

The mathematical model solution for the active motor ratio can be summarized in three cases. As illustrated in Figure 3.35 (left), the first case lacks a solution. The red $r_{substrate}$ curve fails to intersect the blue $f - v$ impedance curve. In the second case, a single solution emerges, wherein the $r_{substrate}$ curve intersects the $f - v$ line at one point, marking the critical active motor ratio of 0.85. The third intersection of curves yields two solutions, from which we must select the stable solution. Figure 3.40 denotes the inception of the actin filament's glide. The plot in Figure 3.41 showcases the outcomes of velocity versus active motility after employing various detachment forces for defective motors.

From these observations, it's apparent that the mathematical model provides valuable insights into the behaviour of actin filaments under different conditions. The absence of a solution in the first case underscores the critical role of intersecting curves in determining motor ratio thresholds. Conversely, the emergence of multiple solutions in the third case highlights the complexity of filament dynamics and the need for discerning stable solutions. These findings not only enhance our understanding of cellular processes but also inform the development of targeted interventions.

Figure 3.40: Model gliding onset for $f_{rupt} = 9.2\text{pN}$. r represents the $r_{substrate}$.

Figure 3.41: Model gliding onset for various detachment forces (f_{rupt}). R represents the $r_{substrate}$.

3.3 Actin under External Force: 2D Simulation

In this section, we delve into the results of simulations focusing on the controllability of actin filaments using an electric field.

3.3.1 Effect on the Trajectories

Figures 3.42 and 3.43 depict the trajectories of actin filaments following the application of various magnitudes of positive and negative force fields. In both figures, when no force is applied, the actin filaments exhibit random movement, leading to unpredictable trajectories. However, upon the application of a negative force field (Figure 3.42), the trajectories of the actin filaments gradually undergo a U-turn away from their initial direction. As the magnitude of the external force field increases, these trajectories manifest sharper U-turns, with successive trajectories aligning closely together in parallel (as observed at $F = -1.0\text{pN}/\mu\text{m}$).

Conversely, when subjected to a positive external force field (Figure 3.43), the trajectories of the actin filaments continue straight without executing a U-turn. With the augmentation of the positive external force field, the trajectories converge to predictable paths, closely aligned in a straight line. This characteristic proves particularly advantageous in the delivery of directed analytes, where precise trajectory control is paramount.

Figure 3.42: Negative force field trajectories

Figure 3.43: Positive force field trajectories

Figure 3.44 illustrates the effectiveness of applying an external force to actin filaments. For both positive and negative force fields, the trajectories of actin filaments become more predictable. Additionally, we observed that the application of an external force field not only facilitates alignment of actin filament trajectories but also increases the distance traveled by the filaments. These findings bear significant implications for fast drug delivery applications, as we will delve into later in this section.

Figure 3.44: Effectiveness of applying an external force field. Left: negative force field, Right: positive force field

3.3.2 Effect on Speed

Figure 3.45 presents the speed analysis for the aforementioned simulation trajectories, juxtaposed with the findings of an experiment [61]. Interestingly, the speed of the actin filament exhibits a slight increase in simulation, whereas in the experiment, the augmentation in speed is more pronounced. This disparity could potentially be attributed to inadvertent heating of the substrate or the motility assay upon application of the external electric field.

Expanding on this observation, it's crucial to consider the various factors that could influence the speed of actin filaments in response to external forces. The discrepancy between simulation and experimental results underscores the complexity of the system and highlights the importance of meticulous experimental design and control. Further investigation into the underlying mechanisms governing actin filament speed under external force fields is warranted to elucidate the observed differences and refine our understanding of the dynamics at play. Such insights will not only enrich our comprehension of cellular processes but also contribute to the development of more effective strategies for drug delivery and biomedical applications.

Figure 3.45: Actin filament speed under influence of an external force field. Left: simulation results, and Right: experimental results adopted from *Zalinge et. al.* [61].

3.3.3 Path Persistence Length

The L_p of the actin filament is calculated from the data of the leading tip trajectory. As explained in Section 2.5, different lengths of b_s can be used by choosing various Δt of the actin filament trajectory. As seen in Figure 3.46, at the beginning of the plot, a small Δt shows a correlation that is significantly different from the first correlation of 1. This is because a small Δt carries more information about the wiggling behaviour of the actin filament, reducing the chance that the trajectory steps are correlated, and hence a sudden drop in the correlation value. In this case, $\Delta t = 0.20 \text{ sec}$ was used.

This value showed a smooth transition from the correlation of 1 to the next and was therefore a better predictor of the average value of the actin filament L_p .

Figure 3.46: Path persistence changes with changing Δt . $\Delta t = 0.2s$ is used to calculate the L_p .

Figure 3.47 shows various trajectories of the actin filament when no external force field is applied. As explained in Figure 3.46, a lower Δt (blue line) is used during the calculation of L_p . Each actin filament follows a unique trajectory. The average movement and L_p of these trajectories without the influence of an external force are compared with other trajectories when an external force is applied.

Figure 3.47: Sample trajectories when no external force is applied. The red line shows the original trajectory from the simulation data at $\Delta t = 0.01s$, and the blue line shows approximate trajectory at $\Delta t = 0.2s$

Figure 3.48 shows the results of the calculation of L_p as demonstrated by Algorithm 6 and implemented in Appendix B.1. The distance covered by the actin filament trajectories is plotted against the mean correlation of each step of the trajectories in Figure 3.47. In Figure 3.48(left), these correlations are shown by light blue dashed dots, and the mean of the five trajectories is shown by the red dashed dots. The L_p of the actin filament at this zero force is 3.7 ± 0.2 as shown in Figure 3.48(right). Some points are lost during logarithmic fitting due to negative correlations of the actin filament ($\log(-x) = NaN$).

Figure 3.48: (Left): The mean correlation of each pair of steps of various trajectories when no external force is applied. (Right): L_p when no external force is applied

Calculating L_p of the actin filament as shown in Figure 3.48(left) is prone to errors. In the process of calculating the correlations of the trajectory steps, the subjects of the trajectory steps (U_{bs}) from which to calculate the correlation drift far apart and the data points from which to compute the mean continue to decrease. Toward the end of the correlation plot, the data become sparse and therefore statistically insignificant and not sufficient for an accurate assessment of L_p . To mitigate this problem, around 10% of the correlation data is used to calculate the L_p of the actin filament. Figure 3.49 shows the calculation of L_p using only 30% of the data in Figure 3.48. The L_p of the actin filament improves slightly to 4.3 ± 0.1 .

Figure 3.49: (Left): The mean correlation of each pair of steps of various trajectories when no external force is applied. (Right): L_p when no external force is applied

Figures 3.50 and 3.52 show the leading tip trajectories of various actin filaments when external forces of $+1.0pN$ and $-1.0pN$ are applied, respectively. Compared to the above trajectories, when no external force is applied, the application of an external force causes the actin filaments to travel in a rather straight path. As a result, calculating the correlations yields values that are close to 1 (≈ 0 after taking \log), along the trajectory, and therefore the correlation values do not decay. The results shown in Figures 3.51 and 3.53 indicate a significant improvement in the actin filament L_p . However, this method may not be an appropriate measure for L_p of almost straight trajectories, since most correlations lie along the horizontal axis close to zero, compromising the fit. Other methods are recommended (*Jonathon Howard book, appendix section [11]*).

Figure 3.50: Sample trajectories when an external force of $+1.0pN$ is applied

Figure 3.51: (Left): The mean correlation of each pair of steps of various trajectories when an external force of $+1pN$ is applied. (Right): L_p when no external force is applied

Figure 3.52: Sample trajectories when an external force of $-1.0pN$ is applied

Figure 3.53: (Left): The mean correlation of each pair of steps of various trajectories when an external force of -1pN is applied. (Right): L_p when no external force is applied

3.3.4 Biosensor Design Insight

The design of biosensors has long been a pursuit at the forefront of biomedical engineering, aiming to revolutionize drug delivery systems and diagnostics. In the quest for more efficient and versatile biosensors, researchers have turned their attention to harnessing external force fields to manipulate biomolecular structures effectively. One promising avenue in this endeavor involves the utilization of actin filaments as key components in biomolecular rectifiers, offering novel possibilities in drug delivery mechanisms.

Figure 3.54 unveils a compelling application of external force fields in the realm of drug delivery devices. By leveraging the ability to control actin filaments through such force fields, researchers can construct designs akin to the microtubule channel-based rectifiers that have been documented in previous studies [82] [83]. However, the creation of an actin-based biomolecular rectifier necessitates more sophisticated microfabricated channels, as depicted in Figure 3.54(a).

In contrast, Figure 3.54(b) presents an equivalent biomolecular rectifier that potentially offers greater efficiency. Remarkably, this design capitalizes on the application of a negative force without the need for intricate or narrow microfabricated channels. Despite its seemingly simpler construction, Figure 3.54(b) doesn't compromise on effectiveness. Notably, the channel size need not be excessively thin. As demonstrated in Figure 3.42, variations in the applied external force can be precisely manipulated to adjust the width through which the filaments traverse. This feature opens avenues for fine-tuning the molecular shuttles' trajectory, allowing them to travel longer distances and at higher velocities.

Figure 3.54: Biomolecular rectifier. (a) A rectifier made without the application of external force. (b) A rectifier made by making use of the applied force.

3.4 Recommendations

Gradient Surface

In Figure 3.55, a gradient surface is depicted, simulating a motility assay involving actin filaments and myosin density. The arrangement of myosin on the surface mimics a gradient function, with density varying across the surface. The purpose of this simulation is to observe the behavior of actin filaments as they traverse this gradient surface.

The trajectories of the simulated actin filaments on the gradient surface are illustrated in the figure. It is observed that when the myosin density forms a narrower channel on the surface, the actin filaments tend to travel longer distances compared to a wider channel. This suggests that the presence of a narrower channel in the gradient surface influences the movement of actin filaments, potentially enhancing their motility.

However, it is important to note that further research is required to validate and confirm these findings. Additional experiments and analysis are necessary to fully understand the impact of gradient myosin density on actin filament trajectories. These preliminary results provide an intriguing indication of the potential effects of the gradient surface, but further investigations are needed to establish the underlying mechanisms and to verify the observed behavior of actin filaments in the presence of such a gradient.

Expanding on these initial observations, it is evident that the gradient surface holds promise as a tool for manipulating actin filament movement in motility assays. By controlling myosin density across the surface, researchers may unlock new possibilities for enhancing the efficiency and directionality of filament transport. However, the complexities of these systems necessitate thorough investigation to elucidate the underlying principles and optimize experimental conditions. Through continued experimentation and analysis, we can harness the full potential of gradient surfaces in guiding actin filament dynamics, advancing our understanding of cellular processes and facilitating the development of innovative biomedical technologies.

Figure 3.55: Gradient surface trajectories of a wide (a) versus a narrow channel (b)

CONCLUSION

“The critical fraction for the outset of the gliding movement of actin filaments can be elucidated by the difference in binding lifetimes of active and defective motors”

Biosensors and Bioelectronics
SAMUEL MACHARIA KANG'IRI *et al.*, 2022

4.1 Biosensor Design	79
4.2 Translation Mechanism	80

4.1 Biosensor Design

To achieve propulsion of actin filaments in an in vitro motility assay, a high percentage of active myosins on the substrate is necessary. Through our 3D simulation, we determined that a motility assay with an active ratio exceeding 90% is required for effective actin filament propulsion. This finding was further supported by our 1D analytical model, which identified a critical active ratio of 80% for progressive filament movement. However, it should be noted that the lower percentage of 80% in the analytical model may be influenced by factors such as Brownian motion and thermal fluctuations, which were not accounted for. Regardless of the length of the actin filament, the ATP supplied, or the motor density of the assay, the high active ratio requirement remains consistent. This suggests that the active ratio of the actomyosin motility assay is the primary factor influencing smooth gliding of the filaments.

When integrating a biosensor with actin and myosin, the presence of defective myosins can impede smooth gliding. Hence, it is crucial to ensure a thorough cleaning process to remove defective motors during the preparation of the in vitro motility assay. Additionally, when selecting the substrate material for the actomyosin motility assay, it is important to choose a material that minimizes myosin denaturation upon

adhesion to the surface. Consideration should be given to the hydrophobicity of the substrate material, as higher hydrophobicity has been associated with a lower population of active myosin molecules. Minimizing the occurrence of defective myosins at the substrate level during the initial stage of preparation can significantly contribute to sustaining active myosins in the assay. The lifetime of active myosin binding is influenced by the presence of defective myosins.

A motility assay with an active myosin ratio ranging from 70% to 90% exhibits the highest number of active myosins binding to the actin filament, and these myosins also spend the longest time bound to the filament. It can be inferred that the binding of active myosins increases in an attempt to overcome the resistance posed by defective myosins. When the active myosin ratio reaches approximately 92%, gliding of the actin filament commences. This implies that even when a few defective myosins are present in the *in vitro* motility assay, a larger population of active myosins can still propel the filament effectively.

Expanding upon our findings, it's evident that achieving optimal conditions for actin filament propulsion in an *in vitro* motility assay demands meticulous attention to various factors. Notably, the interplay between active and defective myosins profoundly influences the efficiency and smoothness of filament movement. Therefore, strategies aimed at maximizing the active myosin ratio while minimizing the presence of defective counterparts are imperative for the success of such assays. Moreover, the choice of substrate material plays a pivotal role in preserving the functionality of myosins, underscoring the importance of substrate selection in assay preparation. By unraveling these intricate dynamics, we pave the way for the development of more robust and reliable biosensors that capitalize on the inherent properties of actin and myosin for diverse biomedical applications.

4.2 Translation Mechanism

The spiral shape formed by the actin filament may be attributed to the presence of defective myosin. In our simulation of the 3D motility assay, we observed that the actin filament was prone to curving during the transition phase. Because the actin filament is semi-flexible, it is easier to move it entirely by pulling rather than pushing. This implies that if the movement of the actin filament is abruptly impeded at the leading tip by a defective myosin, the trailing end may continue to move for a while, making a curve around the impeding fulcrum. For applications involving the movement of cargo through channels, the tendency to form spiral shapes is a defect that reduces the persistence length of the actin filament. Minimizing the denaturation of the adhering myosins on the substrate surface should minimize these spiral shapes. Alternatively, using an actin filament bundle would stiffen the actin filament, thus minimizing the possibility of forming spiral shapes.

The alignment of the actin filament is significantly improved by the application of an electric force field. In our simulation of applying an external force to the actin filaments, we were able to reproduce *in silico* the movement of the actin filaments when they were subjected to an electric field. This enables us to conduct several tests about the electric motility and build up intuition based on the analyzed results. These

insights are important for the design and testing of actin-based devices guided by an electric field.

Expanding upon these observations, it becomes apparent that understanding the intricacies of actin filament behavior is crucial for the development of efficient translation mechanisms. By elucidating the factors contributing to the formation of spiral shapes, such as the presence of defective myosin, and exploring strategies to mitigate their impact, we pave the way for more effective cargo transport systems. Moreover, the utilization of external forces, such as electric fields, presents exciting possibilities for precisely controlling the alignment and movement of actin filaments, thereby facilitating the design and optimization of actin-based devices. Through continued research and experimentation, we can harness these insights to unlock the full potential of actin-based translation mechanisms in various biomedical and engineering applications.

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APPENDIX

“I came here confused about actin and myosin. Now I am still confused, but at a higher level.”

Frontiers in Molecular Motors
SIR ANDREW HUXLEY, 2000

A	Simulation Program	91
A.1	Parameters Used	91
A.2	Main Program Implementation	92
A.3	Generate Normal Random Numbers	96
A.4	Bending Force Calculation	96
A.5	Initial Myosin Binding	96
A.6	Check Myosin-Actin Proximity	97
A.7	Binding Myosin	97
A.8	Myosin Step	98
A.9	Myosin Getting Stuck	98
A.10	Force Actin on Myosin	98
A.11	Forced Myosin Detachment	99
A.12	Force Acting on Actin Beads	100
A.13	Constraints	100
A.14	Renew the Myosin Population	101
A.15	Myosin State Conversion	103
B	Sample Analysis Programs	104
B.1	Path Persistence Length Calculation	104
B.2	Myosin Lifetime Calculation	107
C	Published Works	108
D	Recollections	109

To ensure uninterrupted dissertation flow, the following appendices show important parts of this study that maybe referenced in the main chapters but could not be placed in the main text.

A Simulation Program

A.1 Parameters Used

Table 1: Table of variables and parameters used in the simulation program

Parameter	Particulars	Value
NumAssay	Number of assays	1
NumFilament	Number of filaments used	1
NumBeads	Number of beads	13
NumType	Types of myosins	2
MaxNumIteration	Maximum number of iterations	1E6
AreaRenewDiv	The new area divisions	2E4
OutPutDiv	Steps for every output	2E4
MaxInteractinNum	Maximum interacting filaments	1
seed	Random seed	any integer value
NumTimeStep	Number of simulation time steps	6E6
TimeStepEquil	Time step equilibrium	1E9
MaxNumMotors	Maximum number of myosins	1E6
TimeForceON	Time for force action	1E9
pi	π value used	3.14159265358979
kBT	Energy used	0.0042 $pN \cdot \mu m$
dt	Change in time used	5.0E-7
Tol	Tolerance allowed	1.0E-6
BondLength	Actin bond length	0.25
EI	Actin flexural rigidity	0.073 $pN \cdot \mu m^2$ [49]
DiameterAF	Actin filament diameter	0.006
Motor_Density	Myosin density	3000.0
k	Myosin spring constant	300.0 $pN / \mu m$
Stepsize	Myosin step size	1.0E-2 μm
k_a	The myosin binding rate	40.0 s^{-1}
k_d0	No force rate constant	350.0 s^{-1}
k_t	Rate	2.0 $\mu m^{-1} s^{-1}$
ATP	Adenosine triphosphate	2000.0 μm
k_hp	Forward rate constant	100.0 s^{-1}
k_hm	Backward rate constant	10.0 s^{-1}
delta_x	Binding state-energy barrier distance	-1.86E-3
F_Motor_Detach1	Detachment force for motor type 1	9.2 pN
F_Motor_Detach2	Detachment force for motor type 2	9.2 pN
CaptureRadius	The myosin-actin capture radius	0.020 μm
Type1Ratio	Active myosin ratio	0.60
ExtForceDensity0	External force exerted	0.0 $pN / \mu m$
ExtForceMag	Magnitude of the external force	0.0
XLimit	X-axis limit of the track surface	500.0 μm
OutPutDiv2	Alternative steps for every output	$NINT(0.0005 / dt)$

A.2 Main Program Implementation

```

1 PROGRAM MAIN
2 USE PARAMETERS
3 USE mtmod !Random number generator
4 USE FUNC
5 USE OUTPUT
6 USE PLANAR_TRACK_CONFINEMENT
7 USE UNIFORM_FORCE_X
8 IMPLICIT NONE
9 INTEGER :: seed_Assay, I_Assay, I, J, AreaCounter, EraseCounter, &
10 NumIteration, OutputfileCounter, UnitNumConformation, UnitNumTipXY, &
11 UnitNumMotorStates, UnitNumAreaEraseCounter
12 INTEGER(KIND = Range15):: TS, IM, ActiveMotorIdxOffset, &
13 ActiveMotorIdxEnd
14 INTEGER(KIND = Range15), DIMENSION(MaxAreaNum) :: AddedMotorNum
15 INTEGER, DIMENSION(MaxNumMotors) :: Release_ADP, MotorType
16 !--- 2Motors: 1=Myosin, 2=Defective Myosin ---
17 REAL(KIND = DP) :: IniAngle, UR1, UR2, UR3, gamma_Bead, D_Bead, &
18 XCM, YCM
19 REAL(KIND = DP), DIMENSION(MaxAreaNum) :: AreaOriginX, AreaOriginY, &
20 AreaOriginUx, AreaOriginUy
21 REAL(KIND = DP), DIMENSION(NumBeads) :: XI, YI, ZI, XI_temp, &
22 YI_temp, ZI_temp, FIx, FIy, FIZ, NormRandVector4Beads, &
23 XINormRandVector4Beads, YINormRandVector4Beads, &
24 ZINormRandVector4Beads
25 REAL(KIND = DP), DIMENSION(MaxNumMotors) :: XM, YM, ZM, Elongation
26 REAL(KIND = DP), DIMENSION(NumFilament, MaxNumMotors) :: &
27 ContactState, TempContact
28 REAL(KIND = DP), DIMENSION(MaxNumMotors) :: F_Motor_X, F_Motor_Y, &
29 F_Motor_Z
30 REAL(KIND = DP), DIMENSION(NumBeads, NumFilament) :: X, Y, Z, Fx, &
31 Fy, Fz, Force_Bead_X, Force_Bead_Y, Force_Bead_Z, &
32 XNormRandVector4Beads, YNormRandVector4Beads, ZNormRandVector4Beads
33 LOGICAL :: StateConstraint, StatConfinement
34 LOGICAL, DIMENSION(MaxNumMotors) :: MotorStateUpdate
35 CHARACTER(LEN=30) :: OutFileName
36 seed_Assay = seed
37 !---Calculating Parameters---
38 gamma_Bead = 3.0_DP*pi*0.001_DP*BondLength/ &
39 DLOG(BondLength/DiameterAF)
40 D_Bead = kBT/gamma_Bead
41 !---Output chamber boundary in vtk format---
42 OPEN(10, FILE='InitialCondition.txt')
43 !---Repeat Assay---
44 Loop_Assay: DO I_Assay=1, NumAssay
45 !---Assay Initial Condition---
46 CALL sgrnd(seed_Assay)
47 TS = 0
48 ActiveMotorIdxOffset = 0
49 ActiveMotorIdxEnd = 0
50 AreaCounter = 1
51 EraseCounter = 0
52 OutputfileCounter = 0
53 XM = -100.0_DP
54 YM = 5.0_DP
55 ZM = 0.0_DP
56 Release_ADP = 0
57 IniAngle = 0.0_DP*pi
58 WRITE(10, '(I3,I7,F15.10)') I_Assay, seed_Assay, IniAngle
59 seed_Assay = seed_Assay+1
60 !---OPEN OUTPUT FILE---
61 WRITE(OutFileName, '(A,I3.3,A)') 'ForCheck_A', I_Assay, '.txt'
62 !---Output file for checking the program---
63 OPEN(20, FILE=OutFileName)
64 !---Output file for checking the program---
65 UnitNumConformation = 11
66 WRITE(OutFileName, '(A,I3.3,A)') 'Conformation_A', I_Assay, '.txt'
67 OPEN(UnitNumConformation, FILE=OutFileName)
68 UnitNumTipXY = 12
69 WRITE(OutFileName, '(A,I3.3,A)') 'TipXY_A', I_Assay, '.txt'
70 OPEN(UnitNumTipXY, FILE=OutFileName)
71 UnitNumMotorStates = 13
72 WRITE(OutFileName, '(A,I3.3,A)') 'MotorStates_A', I_Assay, '.txt'

```

```

73 OPEN(UnitNumMotorStates,FILE=OutFileName)
74 UnitNumAreaEraseCounter = 14
75 WRITE(OutFileName,'(A,I3.3,A)') 'AreaEraseCounter_A', I_Assay, '.txt'
76 OPEN(UnitNumAreaEraseCounter,FILE=OutFileName)
77 !---Initial Conformation of Filaments---
78 DO I=1, NumFilament
79     X(NumBeads,I) = 0.0_DP
80     Y(NumBeads,I) = 0.0_DP
81     Z = 0.0125_DP
82     DO J=NumBeads-1, 1, -1
83         X(J,I) = X(J+1,I) + BondLength*DCOS(IniAngle)
84         Y(J,I) = Y(J+1,I) + BondLength*DSIN(IniAngle)
85     END DO
86 END DO
87 !---Initial Motor Location---
88 CALL InitialMotorLocations(ActiveMotorIdxOffset, ActiveMotorIdxEnd, &
89 IniAngle, X, Y, XM, YM, ZM, ContactState, AddedMotorNum, &
90 AreaCounter, AreaOriginX, AreaOriginY, AreaOriginUx, AreaOriginUy, &
91 MotorType)
92 !---Filament-Motor Contact---
93 TempContact = 0.0_DP
94 DO IM=ActiveMotorIdxOffset+1, ActiveMotorIdxEnd
95     CALL CheckMotorFilamentProximity(X, Y, Z, XM(IM), YM(IM), ZM(IM), &
96     ContactState(:,IM), TempContact(:,IM))
97 END DO
98 CALL InitialMotorBinding(ActiveMotorIdxOffset, ActiveMotorIdxEnd, &
99 ContactState, TempContact)
100 !---Calculating Forces upon Motors and Beads---
101 CALL CalculateForceMotor(ActiveMotorIdxOffset, ActiveMotorIdxEnd, &
102 X, Y, Z, XM, YM, ZM, ContactState, F_Motor_X, F_Motor_Y, &
103 F_Motor_Z, Elongation)
104 CALL CalculateForceBead(ActiveMotorIdxOffset, ActiveMotorIdxEnd, &
105 ContactState, Force_Bead_X, Force_Bead_Y, Force_Bead_Z, F_Motor_X, &
106 F_Motor_Y, F_Motor_Z)
107 !---Calculating Forces upon Beads---
108 Fx=Force_Bending(X) + Force_Bead_X + ExtF_X(TS, X, Y, Z)
109 Fy=Force_Bending(Y) + Force_Bead_Y + ExtF_Y(TS, X, Y, Z)
110 Fz=Force_Bending(Z) + Force_Bead_Z + ExtF_Z(TS, X, Y, Z)
111 !---Output Area & Erase Counters---
112 WRITE(UnitNumAreaEraseCounter,*) TS, AreaCounter, EraseCounter
113 !---Various Outputs---
114 CALL OutputConformation(UnitNumConformation,TS,X,Y,Z)
115 CALL OutputTipXY(UnitNumTipXY,TS,X,Y)
116 CALL OutputMotorStates(UnitNumMotorStates, TS, &
117 ActiveMotorIdxOffset, ActiveMotorIdxEnd, X, Y, Z, XM, YM, ZM, &
118 F_Motor_X, F_Motor_Y, F_Motor_Z, ContactState, MotorType)
119 CALL OutputFilamentVTK(I_Assay, OutputfileCounter, X, Y, Z)
120 CALL OutputFilamentPlusEndVTK(I_Assay, OutputfileCounter, X, Y, Z)
121 CALL OutputContactState(I_Assay, OutputfileCounter, &
122 ActiveMotorIdxOffset, ActiveMotorIdxEnd, MotorType, ContactState)
123 CALL OutputIntMotorsVTK(I_Assay, OutputfileCounter, &
124 ActiveMotorIdxOffset, ActiveMotorIdxEnd, MotorType, &
125 ContactState, XM, YM, ZM)
126 CALL OutputMotorsVTK(I_Assay, OutputfileCounter, &
127 ActiveMotorIdxOffset, ActiveMotorIdxEnd, MotorType, XM, YM, ZM)
128 !---End of Initial Setting---
129 !---Start of Time Evolution---
130 Loop_Time: DO TS=1, NumTimeStep
131 !---Update of Motor States---
132 TempContact = 0.0_DP
133 MotorStateUpdate = .FALSE.
134 DO IM=ActiveMotorIdxOffset+1, ActiveMotorIdxEnd
135 !---Forced Detachment of Bound Motors---
136     IF (ContactState(1,IM) >= 1.0_DP) THEN
137         CALL MotorForcedDetachment(F_Motor_X(IM), F_Motor_Y(IM), &
138 F_Motor_Z(IM), ContactState(:,IM), Release_AD(P(IM), &
139 Elongation(IM), MotorType(IM), MotorStateUpdate(IM))
140 !---Filament-Motor Binding---
141     ELSE IF (NINT(ContactState(1,IM)) == 0) THEN
142         CALL CheckMotorFilamentProximity(X, Y, Z, XM(IM), YM(IM), &
143 ZM(IM), ContactState(:,IM), TempContact(:,IM))
144         CALL MotorBinding(ContactState(:,IM), TempContact(:,IM), &

```

```

145     MotorStateUpdate(IM))
146     IF (MotorType(IM) == 1) THEN
147         CALL MotorStep(ContactState(:,IM), TempContact(:,IM))
148     ELSE IF (MotorType(IM) == 2) THEN
149         CALL MotorStuck(ContactState(:,IM), TempContact(:,IM))
150     END IF
151 END IF
152 END DO
153 !---State Conversion of Motors---
154 DO IM=ActiveMotorIdxOffset+1, ActiveMotorIdxEnd
155     IF ((MotorType(IM) == 1) .AND. (MotorStateUpdate(IM) == .FALSE.)) &
156     THEN
157         CALL MotorStateConv(X, Y, Z, F_Motor_X(IM), F_Motor_Y(IM), &
158         F_Motor_Z(IM), ContactState(:,IM), Release_ADP(IM))
159     END IF
160 END DO
161 !---Renew Motor Population---
162 IF (MOD(TS,AreaRenewDiv)==0) THEN
163     CALL RenewMotorPopulation(ActiveMotorIdxOffset, &
164     ActiveMotorIdxEnd, X, Y, XM, YM, ZM, ContactState, AddedMotorNum, &
165     AreaCounter, EraseCounter, AreaOriginX, AreaOriginY, &
166     AreaOriginUx, AreaOriginUy, MotorType)
167 END IF
168 !---Update of Filament States---
169 !---Generating RND Num Matrix---
170 DO I=1,NumFilament
171     CALL NormRNDVector(NumBeads, NormRandVector4Beads)
172     DO J=1,NumBeads
173         XNormRandVector4Beads(J,I) = NormRandVector4Beads(J)
174     END DO
175 END DO
176 DO I=1,NumFilament
177     CALL NormRNDVector(NumBeads, NormRandVector4Beads)
178     DO J=1,NumBeads
179         YNormRandVector4Beads(J,I) = NormRandVector4Beads(J)
180     END DO
181 END DO
182 DO I=1,NumFilament
183     CALL NormRNDVector(NumBeads, NormRandVector4Beads)
184     DO J=1,NumBeads
185         ZNormRandVector4Beads(J,I) = NormRandVector4Beads(J)
186     END DO
187 END DO
188 Loop_Filament: DO I=1, NumFilament
189     DO J=1, NumBeads
190         XI(J)=X(J,I)
191     END DO
192     DO J=1, NumBeads
193         YI(J)=Y(J,I)
194     END DO
195     DO J=1, NumBeads
196         ZI(J)=Z(J,I)
197     END DO
198     DO J=1, NumBeads
199         FIx(J)=Fx(J,I)
200     END DO
201     DO J=1, NumBeads
202         FIy(J)=Fy(J,I)
203     END DO
204     DO J=1, NumBeads
205         FIZ(J)=Fz(J,I)
206     END DO
207     DO J=1, NumBeads
208         XINormRandVector4Beads(J)=XINormRandVector4Beads(J,I)
209     END DO
210     DO J=1, NumBeads
211         YINormRandVector4Beads(J)=YINormRandVector4Beads(J,I)
212     END DO
213     DO J=1, NumBeads
214         ZINormRandVector4Beads(J)=ZINormRandVector4Beads(J,I)
215     END DO
216 !---Unconstrained Movements of Beads---
217     XI_temp = XI + FIx/gamma_Bead*dt + XINormRandVector4Beads * &
218     DSQRT(2.0_DP * D_Bead * dt)
219     YI_temp = YI + FIy/gamma_Bead*dt + YINormRandVector4Beads * &

```

```

220     DSQRT(2.0_DP * D_Bead * dt)
221     ZI_temp = ZI + Fz/gamma_Bead*dt + ZINormRandVector4Beads * &
222     DSQRT(2.0_DP * D_Bead * dt)
223 !---Iteration until Constraint and Confinement are Satisfied---
224     NumIteration = 0
225     StateConstraint = .FALSE.
226     StatConfinement = .FALSE.
227     IterationConstraintConfinement: DO
228         IF (StateConstraint .AND. StatConfinement) EXIT &
229         IterationConstraintConfinement
230         IF (NumIteration > MaxNumIteration) THEN
231             WRITE(*,*) "Too many iterations!"
232             EXIT IterationConstraintConfinement
233         END IF
234         NumIteration = NumIteration + 1
235 !---Filament confinement---
236         StatConfinement = .TRUE.
237         Loop_Bead_Confinement: DO J=1, NumBeads
238             CALL Confinement(XI_temp(J), YI_temp(J), ZI_temp(J), &
239             XI(J), YI(J), ZI(J), StatConfinement)
240         END DO Loop_Bead_Confinement
241 !---Constraint---
242         StateConstraint = .TRUE.
243         Loop_Bond_Constraint: DO J=1, NumBeads-1
244             CALL Constraint(XI_temp(J), YI_temp(J), ZI_temp(J), &
245             XI_temp(J+1), YI_temp(J+1), ZI_temp(J+1), XI(J), YI(J), &
246             ZI(J), XI(J+1), YI(J+1), ZI(J+1), StateConstraint)
247         END DO Loop_Bond_Constraint
248         END DO IterationConstraintConfinement
249 !---Update of Position Variables---
250         DO J=1, NumBeads
251             X(J,I) = XI_temp(J)
252         END DO
253         DO J=1, NumBeads
254             Y(J,I) = YI_temp(J)
255         END DO
256         DO J=1, NumBeads
257             Z(J,I) = ZI_temp(J)
258         END DO
259     END DO Loop_Filament
260 !---Calculating Forces upon Motors and dividing the Force to Beads---
261     CALL CalculateForceMotor(ActiveMotorIdxOffset, ActiveMotorIdxEnd, &
262     X, Y, Z, XM, YM, ZM, ContactState, F_Motor_X, F_Motor_Y, F_Motor_Z, &
263     Elongation)
264     CALL CalculateForceBead(ActiveMotorIdxOffset, ActiveMotorIdxEnd, &
265     ContactState, Force_Bead_X, Force_Bead_Y, Force_Bead_Z, F_Motor_X, &
266     F_Motor_Y, F_Motor_Z)
267 !---Calculating Total Forces upon Beads---
268     Fx=Force_Bending(X) + Force_Bead_X + ExtF_X(TS, X, Y, Z)
269     Fy=Force_Bending(Y) + Force_Bead_Y + ExtF_Y(TS, X, Y, Z)
270     Fz=Force_Bending(Z) + Force_Bead_Z + ExtF_Z(TS, X, Y, Z)
271     IF (MOD(TS, OutPutDiv2)==0) THEN
272         CALL OutputMotorStates(UnitNumMotorStates, TS, &
273         ActiveMotorIdxOffset, ActiveMotorIdxEnd, X, Y, Z, XM, YM, ZM, &
274         F_Motor_X, F_Motor_Y, F_Motor_Z, ContactState, MotorType)
275     END IF
276     IF (MOD(TS, OutPutDiv)==0) THEN
277         OutputfileCounter = OutputfileCounter + 1
278 !---Output Area & Erase Counters---
279         WRITE(UnitNumAreaEraseCounter,*) TS, AreaCounter, EraseCounter
280 !---Various Outputs Filament Conformation---
281         CALL OutputConformation(UnitNumConformation, TS, X, Y, Z)
282         CALL OutputTipXY(UnitNumTipXY, TS, X, Y)
283         CALL OutputFilamentVTK(I_Assay, OutputfileCounter, X, Y, Z)
284         CALL OutputFilamentPlusEndVTK(I_Assay, OutputfileCounter, X, Y, Z)
285         CALL OutputContactState(I_Assay, OutputfileCounter, &
286         ActiveMotorIdxOffset, ActiveMotorIdxEnd, MotorType, ContactState)
287         CALL OutputIntMotorsVTK(I_Assay, OutputfileCounter, &
288         ActiveMotorIdxOffset, ActiveMotorIdxEnd, MotorType, &
289         ContactState, XM, YM, ZM)
290         CALL OutputMotorsVTK(I_Assay, OutputfileCounter, &
291         ActiveMotorIdxOffset, ActiveMotorIdxEnd, MotorType, XM, YM, ZM)
292     END IF

```

```

293 IF (X(1,1) > XLimit) EXIT Loop_Time
294 END DO Loop_Time
295 CLOSE(UnitNumConformation)
296 CLOSE(UnitNumTipXY)
297 CLOSE(UnitNumMotorStates)
298 CLOSE(UnitNumAreaEraseCounter)
299 END DO Loop_Assay
300 CLOSE(10)
301 END PROGRAM MAIN

```

A.3 Generate Normal Random Numbers

```

1 SUBROUTINE NormRNDNum(NRN)
2 USE PARAMETERS, ONLY : DP
3 USE mtmod, ONLY : grnd !From a separate program
4 REAL(KIND = DP), INTENT(OUT) :: NRN
5 REAL(KIND = DP) :: UR1, UR2
6 UR1 = grnd()
7 IF (UR1 == 0.0_DP) UR1 = grnd()
8 UR2 = grnd()
9 NRN = DSQRT(-2.0_DP*DLOG(UR1)) * DCOS(2.0_DP*pi*(UR2))
10 END SUBROUTINE NormRNDNum

```

A.4 Bending Force Calculation

```

1 FUNCTION Force_Bending(Coordinate)
2 USE PARAMETERS, ONLY : DP, NumFilament, NumBeads, BondLength, EI
3 REAL(KIND = DP), DIMENSION(NumBeads, NumFilament) :: Force_Bending
4 REAL(KIND = DP), DIMENSION(NumBeads, NumFilament), &
5 INTENT(IN) :: Coordinate
6 INTEGER :: I, J
7 REAL(KIND = DP) :: F
8 Force_Bending = 0.0_DP
9 DO I=1, NumFilament
10 DO J=2, NumBeads-1
11 F = Coordinate(J+1,I) - 2.0_DP*Coordinate(J,I) + &
12 Coordinate(J-1,I)
13 Force_Bending(J-1,I) = Force_Bending(J-1,I) + (-1.0_DP)*F
14 Force_Bending(J,I) = Force_Bending(J,I) + 2.0_DP*F
15 Force_Bending(J+1,I) = Force_Bending(J+1,I) + (-1.0_DP)*F
16 END DO
17 END DO
18 Force_Bending = Force_Bending*EI/(BondLength**3)
19 END FUNCTION Force_Bending

```

A.5 Initial Myosin Binding

```

1 SUBROUTINE InitialMotorBinding(ActiveMotorIdxOffset, &
2 ActiveMotorIdxEnd, ContactState, TempContact)
3 USE PARAMETERS, ONLY : DP, NumFilament, NumBeads
4 USE mtmod, ONLY : grnd
5 INTEGER(KIND = Range15), INTENT(IN):: ActiveMotorIdxOffset, &
6 ActiveMotorIdxEnd
7 REAL(KIND = DP), DIMENSION(NumFilament, MaxNumMotors), &
8 INTENT(INOUT) :: ContactState, TempContact
9 INTEGER(KIND = Range15) :: IM
10 INTEGER :: II
11 REAL(KIND = DP) :: UR
12 DO IM=ActiveMotorIdxOffset+1, ActiveMotorIdxEnd
13 DO II=1, NumFilament
14 IF ((TempContact(II, IM) >= 1.0_DP) .AND. &
15 (TempContact(II, IM) <= DBLE(NumBeads))) THEN
16 UR = grnd()
17 IF(UR <= 0.1_DP) THEN
18 !---Closer to steady state population of binding motors---
19 ContactState(II, IM) = TempContact(II, IM)

```

```

20         TempContact(II, IM) = 0.0_DP
21         END IF
22     END IF
23 END DO
24 END DO
25 END SUBROUTINE InitialMotorBinding

```

A.6 Check Myosin-Actin Proximity

```

1  SUBROUTINE CheckMotorFilamentProximity(X, Y, Z, XM_IM, YM_IM, &
2 ZM_IM, ContactState_IM, TempContact_IM)
3  USE PARAMETERS, ONLY : DP, MaxNumMotors, NumFilament, NumBeads, &
4  BondLength, CaptureRadius
5  REAL(KIND = DP), DIMENSION(NumBeads, NumFilament), &
6  INTENT(IN) :: X, Y, Z
7  REAL(KIND = DP), INTENT(IN) :: XM_IM, YM_IM, ZM_IM
8  REAL(KIND = DP), DIMENSION(NumFilament), &
9  INTENT(IN) :: ContactState_IM
10 REAL(KIND = DP), DIMENSION(NumFilament), &
11 INTENT(OUT) :: TempContact_IM
12 REAL(KIND = DP) :: Intercept, SqDistance
13 INTEGER(KIND = Range15) :: IM
14 INTEGER :: II, JJ
15 Loop_Filament: DO II=1, NumFilament
16     DO JJ=1, NumBeads-1
17         Intercept = (XM_IM - X(JJ,1))*(X(JJ+1,1) - X(JJ,1)) + &
18             (YM_IM - Y(JJ,1))*(Y(JJ+1,1) - Y(JJ,1)) + &
19             (ZM_IM - Z(JJ,1))*(Z(JJ+1,1) - Z(JJ,1))
20         Intercept = Intercept/BondLength
21         SqDistance = (XM_IM - X(JJ,1))*(XM_IM - X(JJ,1)) + &
22             (YM_IM - Y(JJ,1))*(YM_IM - Y(JJ,1)) + &
23             (ZM_IM - Z(JJ,1))*(ZM_IM - Z(JJ,1)) - Intercept**2
24         IF ((SqDistance <= CaptureRadius**2) .AND.
25             (Intercept >= 0.0_DP) .AND. (Intercept <= BondLength)) THEN
26             TempContact_IM(II) = DBLE(JJ) + Intercept/BondLength
27         END IF
28     END DO
29 END DO Loop_Filament
30 END SUBROUTINE CheckMotorFilamentProximity

```

A.7 Binding Myosin

```

1  SUBROUTINE MotorBinding(ContactState_IM, TempContact_IM, &
2 MotorStateUpdate_IM)
3  USE PARAMETERS, ONLY : DP, NumFilament, dt, k_a
4  USE mtmod, ONLY : grnd
5  REAL(KIND = DP), DIMENSION(NumFilament), &
6  INTENT(INOUT) :: ContactState_IM, TempContact_IM
7  LOGICAL, INTENT(OUT) :: MotorStateUpdate_IM
8  REAL(KIND = DP) :: UR
9  INTEGER :: II
10 UR = grnd()
11 Loop_Filament_ContactCheck: DO II=1, NumFilament
12     IF ((TempContact_IM(II) >= 1.0_DP) .AND. &
13         (NINT(ContactState_IM(II)) == 0)) THEN
14         IF(UR > k_a*dt) THEN
15             TempContact_IM(II) = 0.0_DP
16         ELSE
17             MotorStateUpdate_IM = .TRUE.
18         END IF
19     END IF
20 END DO Loop_Filament_ContactCheck
21 END SUBROUTINE MotorBinding

```

A.8 Myosin Step

```

1  SUBROUTINE MotorStep(ContactState_IM, TempContact_IM)
2  USE PARAMETERS , ONLY : DP, NumFilament, dt, k_a
3  USE mtmod, ONLY : grnd
4  REAL(KIND = DP), DIMENSION(NumFilament), &
5  INTENT(INOUT) :: ContactState_IM, TempContact_IM
6  INTEGER :: II
7  Loop_Filament_ContactCheck: DO II=1, NumFilament
8      IF (TempContact_IM(II) >= 1.0_DP ) THEN
9          ContactState_IM(II) = TempContact_IM(II) + Stepsize/BondLength
10         END IF
11     END DO Loop_Filament_ContactCheck
12 END SUBROUTINE MotorStep

```

A.9 Myosin Getting Stuck

```

1  SUBROUTINE MotorStuck(ContactState_IM, TempContact_IM)
2  USE PARAMETERS , ONLY : DP, NumFilament, dt, k_a
3  USE mtmod, ONLY : grnd
4  REAL(KIND = DP), DIMENSION(NumFilament), INTENT(INOUT) :: &
5  ContactState_IM, TempContact_IM
6  INTEGER :: II
7  Loop_Filament_ContactCheck: DO II=1, NumFilament
8      IF (TempContact_IM(II) >= 1.0_DP ) THEN
9          ContactState_IM(II) = TempContact_IM(II)
10         END IF
11     END DO Loop_Filament_ContactCheck
12 END SUBROUTINE MotorStuck

```

A.10 Force Actin on Myosin

```

1  SUBROUTINE CalculateForceMotor(ActiveMotorIdxOffset, &
2  ActiveMotorIdxEnd, X, Y, Z, XM, YM, ZM, ContactState, &
3  F_Motor_X, F_Motor_Y, F_Motor_Z, Elongation)
4  USE PARAMETERS, ONLY : DP, MaxNumMotors, NumFilament, &
5  CaptureRadius, k
6  REAL(KIND = DP), DIMENSION(NumBeads, NumFilament), &
7  INTENT(IN) :: X, Y, Z
8  REAL(KIND = DP), DIMENSION(MaxNumMotors), &
9  INTENT(IN) :: XM, YM, ZM
10 REAL(KIND = DP), DIMENSION(NumFilament, MaxNumMotors), &
11 INTENT(IN) :: ContactState
12 REAL(KIND = DP), DIMENSION(MaxNumMotors), &
13 INTENT(OUT) :: F_Motor_X, F_Motor_Y, F_Motor_Z
14 INTEGER(KIND = Range15), INTENT(IN):: ActiveMotorIdxOffset, &
15 ActiveMotorIdxEnd
16 REAL(KIND = DP) :: Intercept_Contact, X_Contact, Y_Contact, &
17 Z_Contact
18 REAL(KIND = DP), DIMENSION(MaxNumMotors), &
19 INTENT(OUT) :: Elongation
20 INTEGER(KIND = Range15) :: IM
21 INTEGER :: II, J_Contact
22 F_Motor_X = 0.0_DP
23 F_Motor_Y = 0.0_DP
24 F_Motor_Z = 0.0_DP
25 DO IM=ActiveMotorIdxOffset+1, ActiveMotorIdxEnd
26     IF (ContactState(1,IM) >= 1.0_DP) THEN
27         J_Contact = INT(ContactState(1,IM))
28         Intercept_Contact = ContactState(1,IM) - DBLE(J_Contact)
29         IF (J_Contact >= NumBeads) THEN
30             X_Contact = X(NumBeads,1) + Intercept_Contact * &
31             (X(NumBeads,1) - X(NumBeads-1,1))
32             Y_Contact = Y(NumBeads,1) + Intercept_Contact * &
33             (Y(NumBeads,1) - Y(NumBeads-1,1))
34             Z_Contact = Z(NumBeads,1) + Intercept_Contact * &
35             (Z(NumBeads,1) - Z(NumBeads-1,1))
36         ELSE

```

```

37     X_Contact = X(J_Contact,1) + Intercept_Contact * &
38     (X(J_Contact+1,1) - X(J_Contact,1))
39     Y_Contact = Y(J_Contact,1) + Intercept_Contact * &
40     (Y(J_Contact+1,1) - Y(J_Contact,1))
41     Z_Contact = Z(J_Contact,1) + Intercept_Contact * &
42     (Z(J_Contact+1,1) - Z(J_Contact,1))
43     END IF
44     Elongation(IM) = (XM(IM) - X_Contact)**2 + &
45     (YM(IM) - Y_Contact)**2 + (ZM(IM) - Z_Contact)**2
46     Elongation(IM) = DSQRT(Elongation(IM))
47     F_Motor_X(IM) = k * Elongation(IM) * &
48     (XM(IM) - X_Contact)/Elongation(IM)
49     F_Motor_Y(IM) = k * Elongation(IM) * &
50     (YM(IM) - Y_Contact)/Elongation(IM)
51     F_Motor_Z(IM) = k * Elongation(IM) * &
52     (ZM(IM) - Z_Contact)/Elongation(IM)
53     END IF
54     END DO
55 END SUBROUTINE CalculateForceMotor

```

A.11 Forced Myosin Detachment

```

1  SUBROUTINE MotorForcedDetachment(F_Motor_X_IM, F_Motor_Y_IM, &
2  F_Motor_Z_IM, ContactState_IM, Release_ADP_IM, Elongation_IM, &
3  MotorType_IM, MotorStateUpdate_IM)
4  USE PARAMETERS, ONLY : DP, MaxNumMotors, NumFilament, k, &
5  F_Motor_Detach1, F_Motor_Detach2
6  INTEGER, INTENT(IN) :: MotorType_IM
7  INTEGER, INTENT(INOUT) :: Release_ADP_IM
8  REAL(KIND = DP), INTENT(INOUT) :: F_Motor_X_IM, F_Motor_Y_IM, &
9  F_Motor_Z_IM
10 REAL(KIND = DP), DIMENSION(NumFilament), &
11 INTENT(INOUT) :: ContactState_IM
12 REAL(KIND = DP), INTENT(IN) :: Elongation_IM
13 LOGICAL, INTENT(OUT) :: MotorStateUpdate_IM
14 INTEGER :: II
15 SELECT CASE(MotorType_IM)
16 CASE (1)
17     IF (k*Elongation_IM >= F_Motor_Detach1) THEN
18         F_Motor_X_IM = 0.0_DP
19         F_Motor_Y_IM = 0.0_DP
20         F_Motor_Z_IM = 0.0_DP
21         Scan_Contact_Filament1: DO II=1, NumFilament
22             IF (ContactState_IM(II) >= 1.0_DP) THEN
23                 ContactState_IM(II) = -1.0_DP
24                 Release_ADP_IM = 0
25                 MotorStateUpdate_IM = .TRUE.
26             END IF
27         END DO Scan_Contact_Filament1
28     END IF
29 CASE (2)
30     IF (k*Elongation_IM >= F_Motor_Detach2) THEN
31         F_Motor_X_IM = 0.0_DP
32         F_Motor_Y_IM = 0.0_DP
33         F_Motor_Z_IM = 0.0_DP
34         Scan_Contact_Filament2: DO II=1, NumFilament
35             IF (ContactState_IM(II) >= 1.0_DP) THEN
36                 ContactState_IM(II) = 0.0_DP
37             END IF
38         END DO Scan_Contact_Filament2
39     END IF
40 END SELECT
41 END SUBROUTINE MotorForcedDetachment

```

A.12 Force Acting on Actin Beads

```

1  SUBROUTINE CalculateForceBead(ActiveMotorIdxOffset, &
2  ActiveMotorIdxEnd, ContactState, Force_Bead_X, Force_Bead_Y, &
3  Force_Bead_Z, F_Motor_X, F_Motor_Y, F_Motor_Z)
4  USE PARAMETERS, ONLY : DP, MaxNumMotors, NumFilament
5  REAL(KIND = DP), DIMENSION(NumFilament, MaxNumMotors), &
6  INTENT(IN) :: ContactState
7  REAL(KIND = DP), DIMENSION(NumBeads, NumFilament), &
8  INTENT(OUT) :: Force_Bead_X, Force_Bead_Y, Force_Bead_Z
9  REAL(KIND = DP), DIMENSION(MaxNumMotors), &
10 INTENT(IN) :: F_Motor_X, F_Motor_Y, F_Motor_Z
11 INTEGER(KIND = Range15), INTENT(IN):: ActiveMotorIdxOffset, &
12 ActiveMotorIdxEnd
13 REAL(KIND = DP) :: Intercept_Contact
14 INTEGER(KIND = Range15) :: IM
15 INTEGER :: II, J_Contact
16 Force_Bead_X = 0.0_DP
17 Force_Bead_Y = 0.0_DP
18 Force_Bead_Z = 0.0_DP
19 DO IM=ActiveMotorIdxOffset+1, ActiveMotorIdxEnd
20   Scan_Contact_Filament: DO II=1, NumFilament
21     IF (ContactState(II,IM) >= 1.0_DP) THEN
22       J_Contact = INT(ContactState(II,IM))
23       Intercept_Contact = ContactState(II,IM) - DBLE(J_Contact)
24       IF (J_Contact >= NumBeads) THEN
25         Force_Bead_X(NumBeads,II) = Force_Bead_X(NumBeads,II) + &
26         F_Motor_X(IM)
27         Force_Bead_Y(NumBeads,II) = Force_Bead_Y(NumBeads,II) + &
28         F_Motor_Y(IM)
29         Force_Bead_Z(NumBeads,II) = Force_Bead_Z(NumBeads,II) + &
30         F_Motor_Z(IM)
31       ELSE
32         Force_Bead_X(J_Contact,II) = Force_Bead_X(J_Contact,II) + &
33         (1.0_DP - Intercept_Contact)*F_Motor_X(IM)
34         Force_Bead_Y(J_Contact,II) = Force_Bead_Y(J_Contact,II) + &
35         (1.0_DP - Intercept_Contact)*F_Motor_Y(IM)
36         Force_Bead_Z(J_Contact,II) = Force_Bead_Z(J_Contact,II) + &
37         (1.0_DP - Intercept_Contact)*F_Motor_Z(IM)
38         Force_Bead_X(J_Contact+1,II) = Force_Bead_X(J_Contact+1, &
39         II) + Intercept_Contact*F_Motor_X(IM)
40         Force_Bead_Y(J_Contact+1,II) = Force_Bead_Y(J_Contact+1, &
41         II) + Intercept_Contact*F_Motor_Y(IM)
42         Force_Bead_Z(J_Contact+1,II) = Force_Bead_Z(J_Contact+1, &
43         II) + Intercept_Contact*F_Motor_Z(IM)
44       END IF
45     END IF
46   END DO Scan_Contact_Filament
47 END DO
48 END SUBROUTINE CalculateForceBead

```

A.13 Constraints

```

1  SUBROUTINE Constraint(XItempJ0, YItempJ0, ZItempJ0, XItempJ1, &
2  YItempJ1, ZItempJ1, XIJ0, YIJ0, ZIJ0, XIJ1, YIJ1, ZIJ1, &
3  StateConstraint)
4  USE PARAMETERS, ONLY : DP, Tol, BondLength
5  REAL(KIND = DP), INTENT(INOUT) :: XItempJ0, XItempJ1, YItempJ0, &
6  YItempJ1, ZItempJ0, ZItempJ1
7  REAL(KIND = DP), INTENT(IN) :: XIJ0, XIJ1, YIJ0, YIJ1, ZIJ0, ZIJ1
8  LOGICAL, INTENT(INOUT) :: StateConstraint
9  REAL(KIND = DP) :: XI_tempAB, YI_tempAB, ZI_tempAB, XIAB, YIAB, &
10 ZIAB, BeadsDisSq, DiffSq, gAB, DX, DY, DZ
11 XI_tempAB = XItempJ1 - XItempJ0
12 YI_tempAB = YItempJ1 - YItempJ0
13 ZI_tempAB = ZItempJ1 - ZItempJ0
14 XIAB = XIJ1 - XIJ0
15 YIAB = YIJ1 - YIJ0
16 ZIAB = ZIJ1 - ZIJ0

```

```

17 BeadsDisSq = XI_tempAB**2 + YI_tempAB**2 + ZI_tempAB**2
18 DiffSq = BondLength**2 - BeadsDisSq
19 IF (DABS(DiffSq) > 2.0_DP*Tol*BondLength**2) THEN
20   StateConstraint = .FALSE.
21   gAB = DiffSq / 4.0_DP / (XI_tempAB*XIAB + YI_tempAB*YIAB + &
22     ZI_tempAB*ZIAB)
23   DX = gAB*XIAB
24   DY = gAB*YIAB
25   DZ = gAB*ZIAB
26   XItempJ0 = XItempJ0 - DX
27   YItempJ0 = YItempJ0 - DY
28   ZItempJ0 = ZItempJ0 - DZ
29   XItempJ1 = XItempJ1 + DX
30   YItempJ1 = YItempJ1 + DY
31   ZItempJ1 = ZItempJ1 + DZ
32 END IF
33 END SUBROUTINE Constraint

```

A.14 Renew the Myosin Population

```

1 SUBROUTINE RenewMotorPopulation(ActiveMotorIdxOffset, &
2 ActiveMotorIdxEnd, X, Y, XM, YM, ZM, ContactState, AddedMotorNum, &
3 AreaCounter, EraseCounter, AreaOriginX, AreaOriginY, AreaOriginUx, &
4 AreaOriginUy, MotorType)
5 USE PARAMETERS, ONLY : Range15, DP, MaxNumMotors, NumFilament, &
6 NumBeads, BondLength, HorizontalLength, VerticalLength, &
7 Motor_Density, Type1Ratio
8 INTEGER, DIMENSION(MaxNumMotors), INTENT(INOUT) :: MotorType
9 REAL(KIND = DP), DIMENSION(NumBeads, NumFilament), &
10 INTENT(IN) :: X, Y
11 REAL(KIND = DP), DIMENSION(MaxNumMotors), INTENT(INOUT) :: XM, YM, ZM
12 REAL(KIND = DP), DIMENSION(NumFilament, MaxNumMotors), &
13 INTENT(INOUT) :: ContactState
14 INTEGER(KIND = Range15), DIMENSION(MaxAreaNum), &
15 INTENT(INOUT) :: AddedMotorNum
16 INTEGER, INTENT(INOUT) :: AreaCounter, EraseCounter
17 REAL(KIND = DP), DIMENSION(MaxAreaNum), INTENT(INOUT) :: &
18 AreaOriginX, AreaOriginY, AreaOriginUx, AreaOriginUy
19 INTEGER(KIND = Range15), INTENT(INOUT) :: ActiveMotorIdxOffset, &
20 ActiveMotorIdxEnd
21 INTEGER(KIND = Range15):: IM, AddedMotorCounter
22 INTEGER :: I_Area, JJ, JJJ
23 REAL(KIND = DP) :: XCM, YCM, XM_New, YM_New, UR1, UR2, UR3
24 LOGICAL :: NearBoundary, InNewArea, OutOldArea
25 !---Erase Old Motor Region---
26 OutOldArea = .TRUE.
27 DO JJJ=1, NumBeads
28   IF ((DABS((X(JJJ,1)-AreaOriginX(EraseCounter+1))*AreaOriginUx(&
29     EraseCounter+1) + (Y(JJJ,1)-AreaOriginY(EraseCounter+1))* &
30     AreaOriginUy(EraseCounter+1)) <= 0.5_DP*HorizontalLength + &
31     0.5_DP) .AND. (DABS(-(X(JJJ,1)-AreaOriginX(EraseCounter+1))* &
32     AreaOriginUy(EraseCounter+1) + (Y(JJJ,1)-AreaOriginY(EraseCounter &
33     +1))* AreaOriginUx(EraseCounter+1)) <= 0.5_DP*VerticalLength + &
34     0.5_DP)) THEN
35     OutOldArea = .FALSE.
36   END IF
37 END DO
38 IF (OutOldArea) THEN
39   EraseCounter = EraseCounter + 1
40   ActiveMotorIdxOffset = ActiveMotorIdxOffset + AddedMotorNum(&
41     EraseCounter)
42 END IF
43 !---check if beads are near boundary---
44 XCM=SUM(X(:,1))/DBLE(NumBeads)
45 YCM=SUM(Y(:,1))/DBLE(NumBeads)
46 NearBoundary = .FALSE.
47 DO JJ=1, NumBeads
48   IF (DABS((X(JJ,1)-AreaOriginX(AreaCounter))*AreaOriginUx(&
49     AreaCounter) + (Y(JJ,1)-AreaOriginY(AreaCounter))*AreaOriginUy(&
50     AreaCounter)) >= 0.5_DP*HorizontalLength - 0.5_DP*DBLE(&
51     NumBeads-1)* BondLength - 1.0_DP) NearBoundary = .TRUE.

```

```

52     IF (DABS(-(X(JJ,1)-AreaOriginX(AreaCounter))*AreaOriginY(&
53     AreaCounter) + (Y(JJ,1)-AreaOriginY(AreaCounter))*AreaOriginX(&
54     AreaCounter)) >= 0.5_DP* VerticalLength - 0.5_DP*DBLE(&
55     NumBeads-1)* BondLength - 1.0_DP) NearBoundary = .TRUE.
56 END DO
57 IF (NearBoundary == .TRUE.) THEN
58 !---Generate New Motor Region---
59 AreaCounter = AreaCounter + 1
60 AreaOriginX(AreaCounter) = XCM
61 AreaOriginY(AreaCounter) = YCM
62 AreaOriginX(AreaCounter) = (X(1,1) - X(2,1))/DSQRT((X(1,1) - &
63 X(2,1))* (X(1,1) - X(2,1)) + (Y(1,1) - Y(2,1))*(Y(1,1) - Y(2,1)))
64 AreaOriginY(AreaCounter) = (Y(1,1) - Y(2,1))/DSQRT((X(1,1) - &
65 X(2,1))* (X(1,1) - X(2,1)) + (Y(1,1) - Y(2,1))*(Y(1,1) - Y(2,1)))
66 AddedMotorCounter = 0
67 DO IM=1, NINT(Motor_Density*HorizontalLength*VerticalLength, &
68 Range15)
69 UR1 = grnd()
70 UR2 = grnd()
71 XM_New = XCM + HorizontalLength * (UR1 - 0.5_DP) * AreaOriginX(&
72 AreaCounter) - VerticalLength * (UR2 - 0.5_DP) * AreaOriginY(&
73 AreaCounter)
74 YM_New = YCM + HorizontalLength * (UR1 - 0.5_DP) * AreaOriginY(&
75 AreaCounter) + VerticalLength * (UR2 - 0.5_DP) * AreaOriginX(&
76 AreaCounter)
77 InNewArea = .TRUE.
78 IF (AreaCounter == 1) THEN
79 IF ((DABS((XM_New-AreaOriginX(AreaCounter))*AreaOriginX(&
80 AreaCounter) + (YM_New-AreaOriginY(AreaCounter))*AreaOriginY(&
81 AreaCounter)) <= 0.5_DP*HorizontalLength) .AND. &
82 (DABS(-(XM_New-AreaOriginX(AreaCounter))*AreaOriginY(&
83 AreaCounter) + (YM_New-AreaOriginY(AreaCounter))*AreaOriginX(&
84 AreaCounter)) <= 0.5_DP*VerticalLength)) THEN
85 InNewArea = .FALSE.
86 END IF
87 ELSE
88 DO I_Area = EraseCounter+1, AreaCounter-1
89 IF ((DABS((XM_New-AreaOriginX(I_Area))*AreaOriginX(I_Area) &
90 + (YM_New-AreaOriginY(I_Area))*AreaOriginY(I_Area)) <= &
91 0.5_DP*HorizontalLength) .AND. (DABS(-(XM_New-AreaOriginX(&
92 I_Area))* AreaOriginY(I_Area) + (YM_New-AreaOriginY(&
93 I_Area))* AreaOriginX(I_Area)) <= 0.5_DP*VerticalLength)) THEN
94 InNewArea = .FALSE.
95 END IF
96 END DO
97 END IF
98 IF (InNewArea == .TRUE.) THEN
99 AddedMotorCounter = AddedMotorCounter + 1
100 XM(ActiveMotorIdxEnd + AddedMotorCounter) = XM_New
101 YM(ActiveMotorIdxEnd + AddedMotorCounter) = YM_New
102 ZM(ActiveMotorIdxEnd + AddedMotorCounter) = 0.0_DP
103 UR1 = grnd()
104 IF (UR1 <= Type1Ratio) THEN
105 MotorType(ActiveMotorIdxEnd + AddedMotorCounter) = 1
106 UR2 = grnd()
107 IF(UR2 <= 0.091) THEN
108 ContactState(:,ActiveMotorIdxEnd + AddedMotorCounter) = &
109 -1.0_DP
110 ELSE
111 ContactState(:,ActiveMotorIdxEnd + AddedMotorCounter) = &
112 0.0_DP
113 END IF
114 ELSE
115 MotorType(ActiveMotorIdxEnd + AddedMotorCounter) = 2
116 ContactState(:,ActiveMotorIdxEnd + AddedMotorCounter) = 0.0_DP
117 END IF
118 END IF
119 END DO
120 AddedMotorNum(AreaCounter) = AddedMotorCounter
121 ActiveMotorIdxEnd = ActiveMotorIdxEnd + AddedMotorCounter
122 END IF

```

```
123 END SUBROUTINE RenewMotorPopulation
```

A.15 Myosin State Conversion

```

1  SUBROUTINE MotorStateConv(X, Y, Z, F_Motor_X_IM, F_Motor_Y_IM, &
2  F_Motor_Z_IM, ContactState_IM, Release_ADP_IM)
3  USE PARAMETERS
4  USE mtmod, ONLY : grnd
5  REAL(KIND = DP), DIMENSION(NumBeads, NumFilament), &
6  INTENT(IN) :: X, Y, Z
7  INTEGER, INTENT(INOUT) :: Release_ADP_IM
8  REAL(KIND = DP), DIMENSION(NumFilament), &
9  INTENT(INOUT) :: ContactState_IM
10 REAL(KIND = DP), DIMENSION(NumFilament), INTENT(IN) :: &
11 F_Motor_X_IM, F_Motor_Y_IM, F_Motor_Z_IM
12 REAL(KIND = DP) :: UR, F_Motor_Tangent, k_d
13 INTEGER(KIND = Range15) :: IM
14 INTEGER :: II, J_Contact
15 DO II=1, NumFilament
16   J_Contact = INT(ContactState_IM(II))
17   UR = grnd()
18   SELECT CASE(J_Contact)
19   CASE (-1)
20     IF(UR <= k_hp*dt) THEN
21       ContactState_IM(II) = 0.0_DP
22     END IF
23   CASE (0)
24     IF(UR <= k_hm*dt) THEN
25       ContactState_IM(II) = -1.0_DP
26     END IF
27   CASE (1:)
28     IF (Release_ADP_IM == 0) THEN
29       IF (J_Contact >= NumBeads) THEN
30         F_Motor_Tangent = (F_Motor_X_IM(II)*(X(J_Contact,II) - &
31         X(J_Contact-1,II))+ F_Motor_Y_IM(II)*(Y(J_Contact,II) - &
32         Y(J_Contact-1,II))+ F_Motor_Z_IM(II)*(Z(J_Contact,II) - &
33         Z(J_Contact-1,II)))/BondLength
34       ELSE
35         F_Motor_Tangent = (F_Motor_X_IM(II)*(X(J_Contact+1,II) - &
36         X(J_Contact,II))+ F_Motor_Y_IM(II)*(Y(J_Contact+1,II) - &
37         Y(J_Contact,II))+ F_Motor_Z_IM(II)*(Z(J_Contact+1,II) - &
38         Z(J_Contact,II)))/BondLength
39       END IF
40       k_d = k_d0*DEXP(-F_Motor_Tangent*delta_x/KBT)
41       IF(UR <= k_d*dt) THEN
42         Release_ADP_IM = 1
43       END IF
44     ELSE
45       IF(UR <= k_t*ATP*dt) THEN
46         Release_ADP_IM = 0
47         ContactState_IM(II) = -1.0_DP
48       END IF
49     END IF
50   END SELECT
51 END DO
52 END SUBROUTINE MotorStateConv

```

B Sample Analysis Programs

This section shows the sample analysis programs referenced in this dissertation.

B.1 Path Persistence Length Calculation

```

1 #!/usr/bin/env python
2 # coding: utf-8
3 # Input: trajectory x,y data
4 # Output: persistence length plots
5 #=====
6
7 # Import important libs
8 import numpy as np
9 import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
10 import pandas as pd
11 import os, glob
12 from scipy.optimize import curve_fit
13 plt.style.use("ggplot")
14 cm = 1/2.54
15 #=====
16
17 #Import trajectory data
18 #r = 1.00; v = 7.28 # Set: Active ratio and Filament speed
19 #r = 0.98; v = 6.10
20 #r = 0.96; v = 4.66
21 r = 0.94; v = 3.41
22 R = "{0:.2f}".format(r)
23 conff0 = glob.glob('data/Lp00042/ConfT5S**'+R+'.txt')
24 nm = 'R'+R+'-kBT0.0042'
25 conff0 = sorted(conff0); no = len(conff0); no = no-1
26 print("Imported data list:"); print(conff0)
27 #=====
28
29 # Required parameters
30 beads = 13 # Filament beads (actin)
31 #jmp = 10 ; dt = 'dt0'; Dt = 0.1 # Adjust delta t
32 jmp = 20 ; dt = 'dt2'; Dt = 0.2 # For actin
33 #jmp = 30 ; dt = 'dt0'; Dt = 3 # For microtubule*
34 #=====
35
36 # Calculate the difference and store the values
37 conf0 = [];
38 xy0 = []; xy_1 = []; xy1 = [];
39 xdifff0 = []; ydifff0 = [];
40 for i in conff0:
41     _ = pd.read_csv(i, names=['t','x','y','z'], delim_whitespace=True)
42     xy0_ = _[0::beads] # jump beads
43     xy0.append(xy0_) #
44     _ = xy0_[0::jmp] #
45     _ = _.reset_index(drop=True)
46     conf0.append(_)
47     xdifff0.append(np.diff(_['x']))
48     ydifff0.append(np.diff(_['y']))
49 #=====
50
51 # Plot sample trajectories
52 fig, ax = plt.subplots(1,1, figsize=(10*cm, 10*cm), sharex = True, \
53 sharey = True)
54
55 for i in range(no+1):
56     ax.plot(xy0[i]['x'], xy0[i]['y'], lw=1)
57 ax.minorticks_on()
58 ax.tick_params('both', direction='in', length=8, top=True, \
59 right=True, which='major')
60 ax.tick_params('both', direction='in', length=4, top=True, \
61 right=True, which='minor')
62 ax.set_xlabel('X($\mu\text{m}$)')
63 ax.set_ylabel('Y($\mu\text{m}$)')
64 ax.set_title('$r_{\text{substrate}} = \text{\%}.2f$ | $\Delta t = \text{\%}.2f$ \
65 sec$(r,Dt/jmp)$, fontsize=14)

```

```

66 print("Trajectories:␣")
67 plt.savefig('fig/Traj-'+str(round(r,2))+'-Dt'+str(round(Dt,2))\
68 +nm+'.pdf', format='pdf', bbox_inches='tight')
69 plt.show()
70 #=====
71
72
73 # Calculate unit vector
74 ubx0 = []; uby0 = []
75 ubx_1 = []; uby_1 = []
76 ubx1 = []; uby1 = []
77 for i in range(len(xdiff0)):
78     b0 = np.sqrt(xdiff0[i]**2 + ydiff0[i]**2)
79     ubx0.append(xdiff0[i]/b0)
80     uby0.append(ydiff0[i]/b0)
81 #=====
82
83 # Change numpy array to pandas
84 ub0 = []; ub_1 = []; ub1 = []
85 for i in range(len(ubx0)):
86     ub0.append(pd.DataFrame({'ubx':ubx0[i], 'uby':uby0[i]}))
87 #=====
88
89
90 # Calculate the dot product/correlations
91 _ = []; ds0 = []; dsm0 = []; s0 = []; c = 0;
92 ds0_ = []; dsm_ = []; s_ = []
93
94 # try:
95 #     os.remove('ds_ub_status.txt')
96 # except:
97 #     print("'ds_ub_status.txt' does not exist.")
98
99 for h in range(len(ub0)):
100     for i in range(len(ub0[h])): # Save status for checking
101         print("Ds = %s%i, file=open('ds_ub_status.txt','a')")
102         for j in range(len(ub0[h])):
103             try:
104                 _.append(np.dot(\
105                     ub0[h].loc[j].values,ub0[h].loc[j+i].values))
106             #     print("Ub%s.Ub%s"%(j,j+i), file=open('ds_ub_status.txt','a'))
107             except:
108                 pass #print("No: Ub%s.Ub%s"%(j,j+i))
109             ds0_.append(_) # not necessary to save or is it?
110             dsm_.append(np.mean(_))
111             s_.append(c)
112             _ = [] # empty this bucket
113             c+=1;
114         s0.append(s_)
115         dsm0.append(dsm_)
116         ds0.append(ds0_)
117         c = 0; ds0_ = []; dsm_ = []; s_ = [] # reset stuff
118
119 s0 = np.array(s0)
120 #ds0 = np.array(ds0)
121 dsm0 = np.array(dsm0)
122 #=====
123
124
125 # Calculate the mean of the correlations
126 dfs0 = pd.DataFrame(s0.T)
127 dfdsm0 = pd.DataFrame(dsm0.T)
128 s0_m = dfs0.mean(axis=1)*v*Dt
129 dsm0_m = dfdsm0.mean(axis=1)
130 #=====
131
132
133 # Plot all the persistence length changes and the mean
134 # Plot the persistence length with fitting, showing the Lp
135 fig, ax = plt.subplots(1,2, figsize=(20*cm,10*cm))
136 plt.subplots_adjust(wspace=0.3)

```

```

137 def tenth(x):
138     dftenth = int(round(0.3*(len(x)+.1),0))
139     # 10% and round to the nearest whole
140     return x[:dftenth]
141
142 for i in range(len(conff0)): # All trajectory plots
143     ax[0].plot(tenth(s0_m), tenth(dfdsm0[i]), marker='o', \
144     markersize=3, ls='--', lw=1, \
145     color='lightblue', markerfacecolor='lime', label='_nolegend_')
146
147 ax[0].plot(tenth(s0_m), tenth(dsm0_m), marker='o', \
148 markersize=3, ls='--', lw=1, \
149 color='red', markerfacecolor='lime', label='Average') # Mean plot
150 #ax[0].set_yticks(np.arange(-1,1.1,0.25)) # For actin
151 ax[0].minorticks_on()
152 ax[0].tick_params('both', direction='in', top=True, right=True, \
153 length=8, which='major')
154 ax[0].tick_params('both', direction='in', length=4, which='minor')
155 ax[0].set_xlabel(r'$(S\cdot V\cdot\Delta t)\cdot\mu_m$', fontsize=14)
156 ax[0].set_ylabel(r'$\langle\cos(\Delta\theta)\rangle_s$', fontsize=14)
157 ax[0].set_title('$r_{substrate}=\%.2f$|$\Delta t=\%.2f\backslash$
158 sec$'%(r,Dt), fontsize=14)
159
160 #-----
161 # Calculate the log of y and then do fitting
162 x = s0_m
163 y = dsm0_m
164
165
166 x = tenth(x); print(x)
167 y = tenth(y); print(y)
168
169 y = np.log(y); print(y)
170 df_xy = pd.DataFrame({'x':x, 'y':y})
171 df_xy = df_xy.dropna() # remove any NaN
172 x = np.array(df_xy['x']); print(x)
173 y = np.array(df_xy['y']); print(y)
174
175 ax[1].plot(x,y, marker='o', c='r', ls='--', lw=1, markerfacecolor='lime')
176
177 def func(x,Lp): # fitting function
178     return 1*(-x/(2*Lp))
179 params, covs = curve_fit(func, x, y)
180 y = func(x,*params)
181 perr = np.sqrt(np.diag(covs[0])) # Error on params
182 #-----
183 ax[1].plot(x, y, label=r'Lp=\%.4f$\pm$\%.4f$\mu_m$\backslash$
184 %(params[0],perr)) # curve fit
185 #ax[1].set_yticks(np.arange(-3,0.1,0.5))
186 ax[1].minorticks_on()
187 ax[1].tick_params('both', direction='in', top=True, right=True, \
188 length=8, which='major')
189 ax[1].tick_params('both', direction='in', length=4, which='minor')
190 ax[1].set_xlabel(r'$(S\cdot V\cdot\Delta t)\cdot\mu_m$', fontsize=14)
191 ax[1].set_ylabel(r'$\log\langle\cos(\Delta\theta)\rangle_s$', \
192 fontsize=14)
193 ax[1].set_title('$r_{substrate}=\%.2f$|$\Delta t=\%.2f\backslash$
194 sec$'%(r,Dt), fontsize=14)
195
196 ax[1].legend()
197 plt.savefig('fig/LpF-'+str(round(r,2))+'-Dt'+str(round(Dt,2))\
198 +nm+'.pdf', format='pdf', bbox_inches='tight')
199 plt.show()
200 #=====

```

You may fork the code in [B.1](#) on [Github](#).

B.2 Myosin Lifetime Calculation

```

1 #!/usr/bin/env python
2 # coding: utf-8
3 # Input: motor states
4 # Output: lifetime data
5 #=====
6 import numpy as np
7 import pandas as pd
8 import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
9 from ast import literal_eval
10 import glob
11
12 #=====
13 files = glob.glob('MotorStates_Ts0.**.txt')
14 files = sorted(files, key=lambda x:x[-20:])
15
16 #=====
17 columns = ['ts','im','mt','c','xc','yc','zc','xm','ym','zm',\
18 'fx','fy','fz']
19 # ts = timestep, im = motor index, mt = motor type (active = 1,\
20 # defective = 2)
21 # c = contact state, xc|yc|zc = binding motor head position,\
22 # xm|ym|zm = binding motor root position
23 # fx|fy|fz = xyz force experienced by motor
24
25 for r in files:
26     print(r)
27     ms = pd.read_csv(r, names=columns, delim_whitespace=True)
28
29     #=====
30     # Separate active motor and defective binding motors.
31     ms_act = ms[ms.mt == 1]
32     ms_act = ms_act.reset_index(drop=True)
33     ms_def = ms[ms.mt == 2]
34     ms_def = ms_def.reset_index(drop=True)
35
36     #=====
37     # Lifetime metric: during one lifetime, a binding motor, ( xm,ym)
38     # must retain index 'im'
39     # and also contact state, 'c' in the next immediate time step 'ts'
40     #act_xy = np.around( ms_act[['im','c','xm','ym']], 6).values.tolist()
41     #def_xy = np.around( ms_def[['im','c','xm','ym']], 6).values.tolist()
42
43     ms_act = ms_act.drop(['ts','mt','xc','yc','zc','zm','fx','fy',\
44 'fz'],1) # remove the unused columns
45     ms_act = ms_act.groupby(ms_act.columns.tolist(), \
46 as_index=False).size() # count duplicated rows
47     ms_act.rename(columns={'size':'lyf'}, inplace=True)
48
49     ms_def = ms_def.drop(['ts','mt','xc','yc','zc','zm','fx','fy',\
50 'fz'],1)
51     ms_def = ms_def.groupby(ms_def.columns.tolist(), \
52 as_index=False).size()
53     ms_def.rename(columns={'size':'lyf'}, inplace=True)
54
55     #=====
56     # columns will be: |im|c|xm|ym|life| *
57     ms_act.to_csv(r[12:-4]+'act_with_lyf.csv', header=False, \
58 index=False, float_format='%.6f') # idx,contact,x,y,life
59     #-----
60     try:
61         ms_def.to_csv(r[12:-4]+'def_with_lyf.csv', header=False, \
62 index=False, float_format='%.6f') # idx,contact,x,y,life
63     except:
64         print('Saving um2 passed: ' + r) # No defective motors in R =1.0

```

Other programs are available on Github [\[2018/19\]](#) [\[2020\]](#) [\[2021\]](#).

C Published Works

The following are related presentations and publications that were done before the final submission of this dissertation:

1. **“The Impact of Defective Motors on Biosensor Integrated with Actin Filaments and Myosin”**
Samuel Macharia Kang’iri and Takahiro Nitta
 PRESENTATION [20189G]: BSJ2020, *Biophysical Society of Japan*, 2020
[\[https://doi.org/10.2142/biophys.60.S1\]](https://doi.org/10.2142/biophys.60.S1)
2. **“Effect of defective motor proteins on the performance of biosensors integrated with motorproteins”**
Samuel Macharia Kang’iri, Dan V. Nicolau, and Takahiro Nitta
 PRESENTATION [P2.116]: BIOSENSORS2021, *Elsevier - Biosensors and Bioelectronics*, 2021
[\[https://app.oxfordabstracts.com/events/1657/program-app/session/12709\]](https://app.oxfordabstracts.com/events/1657/program-app/session/12709)
3. **“A Mathematical Model Predicting Gliding Speed of Actin Molecular Shuttles over Myosin Motors in the Presence of Defective Motors”**
Samuel Macharia Kang’iri and Takahiro Nitta
 BOOK CHAPTER/PAPER: *Springer - BICT*, 2021
[\[https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-92163-7_17\]](https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-92163-7_17)
4. **“Simulations of Actomyosin-Based Molecular Shuttles Controlled by External Force”**
Samuel Macharia Kang’iri, Andrew Salem, Dan V. Nicolau, and Takahiro Nitta
 PAPER: *IEEE - MHS*, 2021
[\[https://doi.org/10.1109/MHS53471.2021.9767188\]](https://doi.org/10.1109/MHS53471.2021.9767188)
5. **“Effects of defective motors on the active transport in biosensors powered by biomolecular motors”**
Samuel Macharia Kang’iri, Andrew Salem, Dan V. Nicolau, and Takahiro Nitta
 PAPER: *Elsevier - Biosensors and Bioelectronics*, 2022
[\[https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bios.2022.114011\]](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bios.2022.114011)
6. **“Motility resilience of molecular shuttles against defective motors”**
Samuel Macharia Kang’iri and Takahiro Nitta
 PAPER: *IEEE - Transaction on Nanobioscience*, 2022
[\[https://doi.org/10.1109/TNB.2022.3170562\]](https://doi.org/10.1109/TNB.2022.3170562)
7. **“Linking path and filament persistence lengths of microtubules gliding over kinesin”**
May Sweet, Samuel Macharia Kang’iri, and Takahiro Nitta
 PAPER: *Nature - Scientific Reports*, 2022
[\[https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-022-06941-x\]](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-022-06941-x)

D Recollections

Figure D.1: Supervisors and I (2019). **(a)** In Nagoya Castle Japan. **Left:** Prof. Dan V. Nicolau from McGill University, Canada. **Middle:** Sam Macharia from Dedan Kimathi University of Technology, Kenya. **Right:** Prof. Takahiro Nitta from Gifu University, Japan. **(b)** In Gusto Restaurant Gifu Japan. **Left:** Prof. Minoru Sasaki from Gifu University, Japan. **Right:** Sam Macharia from Dedan Kimathi University of Technology, Kenya.

Figure D.2: Research work (2020, 2021). **(a)** A typical lab day in Prof. Nitta Lab, Gifu University, Japan, here doing data analysis. **(b)** A press release in Gifu University [<https://www.gifu-u.ac.jp/news/research/20220207.pdf>] after a publication [63].

Figure D.3: A photograph after the defence presentation exam (2022).

INDEX

A		E		Microtubule	5
Actin	5	External force field	69	Molecular shuttle	10, 13
Actin high flexibility	15	F		Myosin hydrolysis	5
Actin high speed	18	Fast drug delivery	70	N	
Analyte	10	H		Negative correlation	72
B		Heavy meromyosin	3	P	
Binding estimate	59	I		Path persistence length	73
Binding myosin	54	In silico motility assay	20, 37	Persistence length	37, 46
Bio-MEMS	6	L		S	
Biocomputation	12	Lifetime estimate	59	Stationary-motile	
Biosensor	10	Lifetime of myosin	61	transition	65
Brownian dynamics	23	Light meromyosin	3	T	
C		M		Thermal effects	23
Conformation	42	Mathematical model	64	W	
Correlation	71	Michaeli Menten	30	Wiggling correlation	71
D					
Directed analyte	69				

The End

A decorative flourish consisting of two symmetrical, swirling lines that meet at the center, with a wavy line underneath.